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D3.6 – Selection of the best chemical treatment for the degradation of halogenated pollutants and PFAS from groundwater and performance at field-scale

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Executive Summary

The present study conducted as part of the H2020 PROMISCES project evaluates the effectiveness of advanced oxidation and reduction processes for degrading organic pollutants, specifically PFAS and chlorinated solvents, in groundwater. The research focused on two sites in northern Spain: one contaminated by chlorinated solvents and another by PFAS.

Laboratory tests revealed relatively promising results. For chlorinated solvents, the combination of persulfate (PS) and sulphidated nano-zero valent iron (S-nZVI) showed the highest removal efficiency. In the case of PFAS, the combination of PS activated with ferrate (Fe(VI)) proved to be the most effective, with optimized ratios of 10 mM PS + 1 mM Fe(VI) achieving the highest removal rates while maintaining a stable pH. Column experiments simulated transport conditions of the aquifer and demonstrated that the PS + Fe(VI) treatment achieved PFAS removal rates ranging between 67-97%.

Also, an on-site approach for groundwater treatment based on ultrasonic cavitation was tested at lab-scale. At first, the cavitation-based treatment was conducted on PFOS solution to optimize the reactor setup and understand its effectiveness. Subsequently, the method was implemented on AFFF formulation and real PFAS-contaminated groundwater samples. Under optimal conditions, a complete removal of PFAS (for PFOS, AFFF and contaminated groundwater samples) was found to be feasible within only 240 min of treatment.

The in-situ chemical oxidation (ISCO) demonstrated at field scale began with tracer tests that revealed heterogeneous subsurface conditions with varying flow velocities and preferential pathways. Subsequently, ISCO treatments using PS + Fe(VI) showed the potential capacity of the oxidation reagents to desorb PFAS from the soil matrix, such as 6:2-FTS and PFOS, which masked the overall PFAS removal in groundwater achieved by the oxidant reagents. Medium efficiencies of PFAS removal were observed in GW from the injection well, over 82% for long-chain PFAS ($C > 6$) and 72% for short-chain PFAS ($C \leq 6$). In the same line, the overall toxicity reduction observed in all wells ranged from 18 to 89%, suggesting that even the full mineralization of PFAS cannot be assured, at least no degradation by-products (i.e., ultra short PFAS) were being formed during the oxidation process with toxic effects superior to those of the parent compounds.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that the combination of PS and Fe(VI) has the potential of reducing the PFAS content from GW via an in-situ remediation strategy, but further field scale studies are still required to assess its effectiveness and assure removal mechanisms. The optimized treatment showed medium removal efficiencies in both laboratory and field conditions, with potential for further improvements. Moreover, knowledge gaps still present in this ISCO strategy are the following: the extent of PFAS sorption to the iron oxides generated during the treatment, the potential of ferric precipitates to cause clogging issues in the aquifer, and to what extent the PFAS sorbed to the soil matrix are mobilized due to the remediation treatment. PROMISCES project allowed to test at real scale an in-situ strategy for PFAS-contaminated groundwater, but more research is needed in order to elucidate if this might be an effective solution for groundwater decontamination of PFAS.

List of abbreviations

6:2-FTS	6:2-fluorotelomersulfonic acid
AFFF	Aqueous Film Forming Foams
CS	Case Study
CW	Groundwater
CTD	Conductivity Temperature Depth
DW	Drinking Water
E _{EO}	Electrical energy per order
EBT	Evidence-Based Toxicity
EC	Electrical Conductivity
GC	Gas Chromatography
DCE	Dichloroethylene
ISCO	In-situ Chemical Oxidation
iPM(T)s	industrial Persistent, Mobile and Toxic substances
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
MgAc	Mg-aminoclay
MS	Mass Spectrometry
MW	Monitoring Well
nZVI	nano Zero-Valent Iron
OC	Organochlorine
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
PFBA	Perfluorobutanoic acid
PCE	Perchloroethylene
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFBS	Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid
PFDA	Perfluorodecanoic acid
PFHpA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid
PFHxS	Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctane sulfonate
PFPeA	Perfluoropentanoic acid
PFUdA	Perfluoroundecanoic acid
PS	Persulfate
PT	Purge and Trap
SPE	Solid Phase Extraction
SW	Surface Water
TCE	Trichloroethylene
TOC	Total Organic Carbon
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds

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1 Introduction

Groundwater (GW) is a crucial and reliable freshwater resource. However, it is highly vulnerable to pollution and can retain contaminants for extended periods. There is growing concern about the contamination of GW with organic compounds, which can infiltrate aquifers through various pathways. Groundwater in industrial areas is particularly affected, with significant levels of pollutants such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and other industrial chemicals. The increasing presence of industrial persistent, mobile and toxic compounds (iPM(T)s) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), presents a critical barrier to advancing sustainable water management and circular economy. These contaminants pose serious risks to both human health and the environment. Remediating groundwater contaminated with these substances presents significant challenges due to their persistence, mobility, and potential toxicity to human health. These characteristics make them difficult to remove and mitigate. Within the H2020 project PROMISCES, this study evaluates the effectiveness of advanced oxidation and reduction processes for degrading organic pollutants, more specifically PFAS and chlorinated solvents, from groundwater. Eight innovative oxidation treatments, including persulfate (PS), ferrous sulphate, sulphidated nano-zero valent iron (S-nZVI), and potassium ferrate (Fe(VI)), as well as their combinations, and ultrasonic cavitation, were investigated for their potential in on-site or in situ remediation approaches for PFAS and OC-polluted groundwaters.

2 Objectives

The main objective of the present study was to develop and optimize sustainable remediation technologies for the elimination of PFAS and halogenated pollutants from groundwater, emphasizing in-situ and on-site treatments for real groundwater scenarios. These real GW scenarios correspond to two aquifers located in the north of Spain (**Case Study CS#7**).

The ambition of the present study was **to develop technologies for the remediation of PFAS and other iPM(T) contamination in GW** and the specific performance targets were: (i) removal of over 5 PFAS compounds; (ii) removal of more than 10 iPM(T) substances; and (iii) an iPM(T) removal efficiency of over 90%.

Figure 1 : Groundwater remediation layout in CS#7 (source: KWB)

3 Site description

Case study CS#7 is composed of two independent sites. One of the sites is an aquifer polluted by chlorinated solvents coming from diffuse pollution of the surrounding industrial activities (Site 1), while the other is an aquifer affected by perfluorinated compounds (PFAS) from aqueous film forming foams used in fire-fighting activities (Site 2). The first site was the original site foreseen during the proposal stage. However, because of the natural degradation of the PFAS detected in this first site between the preparation of the proposal and the start of the project implementation, it was decided to add a second site polluted by PFAS to the case study. As part of Task 3.4, bench-scale remediation treatment tests were conducted using groundwater from both aquifers to address contamination by two different pollutant types. However, field testing was limited to the PFAS-polluted aquifer (Site 2).

In summary, the in-situ strategy for remediation based on persulfate activated with ferrate (VI), among other oxidant options, was tested for Site 1 (only at lab-scale) and Site 2 (both lab and field testing). Ultrasonic cavitation was tested for Site 2 at lab-scale.

The complete description of both sites and its characterization is public and can be consulted in the PROMISCES Deliverable D2.2. *Characterization of PFAS and chlorinated solvent contamination in two aquifers in Spain.*

3.1 Chlorinated solvent polluted aquifer

This site (Site 1) covers an area of 15,300 m². The subsoil is mainly composed of silt, with varying proportions of sand and clay depending on the depth. Between 7 and 8 meters deep, there is a layer of gravel with silty sand, which is highly permeable. The maximum hydraulic gradient is directed southwest, and the groundwater depth ranges from 5.5 to 6.5 meters.

The presence of chlorinated solvents at this site is due to diffuse pollution from nearby industrial activities affecting the soil and groundwater. The site, covering approximately one hectare, is paved and equipped with six wells: one groundwater well (called Pozo), and five smaller monitoring wells (MW2, MW6, MW7, MW14 and MW18). The groundwater gradient is predominantly from northeast to the southwest, with depths ranging from 5.5 to 6.5 meters.

In 2019, a fire at a nearby hazardous waste treatment plant led to the use of PFAS-containing Aqueous Film Forming Foams (AFFF), temporarily introducing PFAS into the aquifer alongside the chlorinated solvents. However, since September 2021, just before the start of the current project, PFAS concentrations in all groundwater wells fell below detection limits. Due to the site's involvement in ongoing legal proceedings and restrictions on site intervention by authorities, a second site, designated as Site 2, was added to Case Study #7. Full-scale remediation was conducted at Site 2.

Figure 2 : Site 1 layout showing the groundwater sampling points and water flow direction (above) and geological profile B-B' (below)

The groundwater physical-chemical analysis revealed significant variability among sampling wells. Wells MW-6 and MW-14 exhibited high conductivity values (57.6 and 11.6 mS/cm, respectively), a pH of around 5.4, and elevated Eh levels (69.2 and 158.7 mV, respectively), with TOC below 50 mg/L. High conductivity in these wells could be attributed to industrial contaminants like zinc. In contrast, wells MW2 and "Pozo" showed a neutral pH around 7.4, lower conductivity (1 mS/cm), and lower TOC values (3 and <2 mg/L, respectively). Chemical analysis indicated elevated levels of chloride and metals such as Fe, Ni, and Cu in MW-6 and MW-14, which may influence the efficiency of proposed advanced oxidation processes (Figure 3).

As for the chlorinated solvents (and other VOC), 20 out of the 59 studied chemicals were identified in the samples analysed (Table 1). The extraction wells that showed the highest concentrations of VOC were those in which the conductivity and other ions were greater. The most abundant chlorinated solvents were trichloroethylene (TCE) and tetrachloroethylene (perchloroethylene, PCE), with concentration levels between 0.3 and 8 µg/L, followed by other VOC such as chloromethane, dichloroethylene, or BTEX.

Table 1 : Chlorinated solvents and other VOC detected (in at least one sampling point) and concentrations measured in Site 1. All expressed in µg/L.

Compounds	LOD	LOQ	Lab blank	Sampling blank	MW2	POZO	MW14	MW6
Chloromethane	0.053	0.177	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1.354
CIS-1,2-dichloroethylene	0.012	0.041	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.844	0.450
Chloroform	0.090	0.300	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOQ	<LOD
Benzene	0.011	0.036	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0,665
Trichloroethylene	0.020	0.065	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	7.808	2,864
Toluene	0.059	0.196	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.202	1.959
Tetrachloroethylene	0.046	0.153	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	6.332	0.283
Ethylbenzene	0.004	0.014	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.874
M-xylene/P-xylene	0.004	0.012	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.669
O-xylene	0.003	0.010	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1.483
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	0.004	0.015	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.312
1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene	0.004	0.013	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.601
1,2-Dichlorobenzene	0.003	0.010	<LOD	<LOD	0.275	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Naphthalene	0.011	0.037	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.257

Figure 3 : VOC and metal/metalloid concentrations in MW6 and MW14 from Site 1.

3.2 PFAS polluted aquifer

The Site 2 covers approximately 4,000 m², with 50% of its surface paved with concrete and lies over quaternary alluvial and colluvial sediments, which rest unconformably on bedrock consisting of fractured granodiorite and granite with narrow porphyritic dykes. From top to bottom, a sequence of permeable and impermeable layers is present, with the aquifer bottom at around 10 meters, where unweathered granite begins. The main groundwater-bearing unit consists of detrital sediments and weathered bedrock with high hydraulic conductivity due to intergranular porosity. A secondary unit is represented by the unweathered bedrock, where water flows through a network of fractures. The groundwater depth ranges from 5.5 to 6.0 meters.

Since the 1990s, the site has been used for fire-fighting training, which includes the use of PFAS-containing Aqueous Film-Forming Foams (AFFF). Fire-fighting training activities occur roughly once or twice a month. These activities pose a risk of PFAS contamination, as AFFF has been known to contribute to PFAS pollution at locations such as airports and military bases (Mueller & Yingying, 2020). Despite being partially paved, the site allows for the infiltration of contaminants into the soil and groundwater. Figure 4 shows the active release areas where AFFF is currently used, and the abandoned release area where it was previously used. Between September and November 2021, six wells (MW1 to MW6) were installed as part of another EU-funded project, [LIFE SOuRCE](#). All wells reach a depth of approximately 10 meters. Four wells were placed in the active areas (MW1, MW2, MW3, MW4), one downstream from these active areas (MW5), and one in the abandoned release area (MW6). The groundwater flow direction at the site is predominantly from the northwest to the southeast.

Figure 4 : Site 2 layout showing the groundwater sampling points, water flow direction (above) and PFAS fingerprint observed in groundwater at each MW (below).

The physical-chemical characterization of groundwater showed a pH around 7 or slightly below, conductivities ranging from 355 to 915 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, dissolved oxygen up to 1.93 mg/L, Eh between 93 and 143 mV, and TOC between 2 and 6 mg/L. Analytical methods for this full site characterization and further data are included in Deliverable D2.2. Chemical analysis revealed minimal metal presence and no pollution from hydrocarbons or organochlorines compounds (Annex II). However, PFAS analysis detected 19 compounds, including carboxylic acids (PFCA), sulfonic acids (PFSA), and fluorotelomer sulfonates (FTSA), with concentrations ranging from 45 ng/L to 126 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and a maximum carbon chain length of 12. New PFAS compounds like, 6:2 diPAP, 8:2 diPAP, ADONA, EtFOSA, EtFOSAA, FOSAA, MeFOSAA, MeFOSA, HFPO-DA (Gen-X), PFMOAA, PFMOPrA, PFMOBA, PFO2HxA, PFO3OA and PFO4DA were not detected (Table 2). The highly mobile PFPeA was found at concentrations between 0.009 and 112 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and PFOS between 0.79 ng/L and 1.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$.

Table 2 : Concentrations of PFAS detected in groundwater samples from Site 2, and limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), all expressed in ng/L.

	LOD	LOQ	MW01	MW02	MW03	MW04	MW05	MW06
PFBA	0.042	0.14	240.38	50.32	27.22	1247.32	98.31	2.27
PFPeA	0.042	0.14	1185.19	291.33	125.77	112071.37	1049.13	9.87
PFHxA	0.045	0.15	1069.55	234.89	132.45	9137.00	790.79	6.83
PFHpA	0.048	0.16	400.23	93.73	30.35	1548.99	338.14	6.05
PFOA	0.045	0.15	47.12	30.76	15.12	504.23	57.62	6.02
PFNA	0.039	0.13	3.52	8.24	1.78	66.94	3.88	0.36
PFDA	0.297	0.99	2.95	5.02	< LOQ	62.47	< LOQ	< LOQ
PFUnA	0.363	1.21	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ
PFDoA	0.504	1.68	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOQ	< LOD	< LOD	< LOQ
PFTTrDA	0.504	1.68	< LOQ	< LOD	< LOQ	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
PFTeDA	1.632	5.44	< LOD	< LOD	< LOQ	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
PFHxDA	0.624	2.08	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
PFODA	1.488	4.96	< LOD	< LOD	< LOQ	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
PFBS	0.093	0.31	36.62	17.75	9.38	128.84	48.32	3.72
PFPeS	0.09	0.30	34.10	7.09	1.29	148.77	39.34	0.41
PFHxS	0.093	0.31	411.50	83.30	10.00	889.69	244.69	4.18
PFHpS	0.12	0.40	6.78	6.48	< LOQ	37.52	10.95	< LOQ
PFOS	0.111	0.37	413.61	1098.24	104.27	444.74	97.42	5.91
PFNS	0.147	0.49	2.30	7.16	0.53	1.70	< LOQ	< LOQ
PFDS	0.138	0.46	1.14	2.35	< LOD	< LOQ	< LOD	< LOD
PFDoS	0.327	1.09	< LOD	< LOQ	< LOQ	1.22	< LOD	< LOD
10:2 FTSA / H4-PFDoDS	0.327	1.09	6.29	3.20	2.55	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
4:2 FTSA / H4-PFHxS	0.093	0.31	2.87	< LOD	< LOD	3.22	< LOD	< LOD
6:2 FTSA / H4-PFOS	0.111	0.37	58.21	33.38	48.66	213.07	15.79	< LOD
8:2 FTSA / H4-PFDeS	0.138	0.46	8.54	15.08	9.78	23.42	0.83	< LOD
Sum PFAS¹ (µg/l)			3.93	1.99	0.52	126.5	2.80	0.05

Regarding the analysis of PFAS in the soil column, 11 compounds were detected at concentrations exceeding the LOQ, all belonging to the same chemical classes found in water: perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCA), perfluorosulfonic acids (PFSA), and fluorotelomer sulfonates (FTSA) (Table 3). The detected PFAS had a maximum chain length of 9 carbons. It was generally observed that long-chain PFAS tend to be retained in the unsaturated zone due to their air-water partitioning coefficients and the lower solubility. Moreover, PFAS concentrations decreased with depth in the aquifer, while short-

¹ Target method for PFAS including 41 substances

chain PFAS concentrations increased, likely due to the degradation of long-chain PFAS, such as FTSA (Figure 5). Finally, emerging PFAS such as 10:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, 4:2 FTSA, 6:2 diPAP, 8:2 diPAP, ADONA, EtFOSA, EtFOSAA, FOSAA, MeFOSAA, MeFOSA, HFPO-DA (Gen-X), PFMOAA, PFMOPrA, PFMOBA, PFO2HxA, PFO3OA, and PFO4DA were not detected in soil.

Table 3 : Concentrations of PFAS detected in soil samples from Site 2, and limits of detection (MLOD) and quantification (LOQ), all expressed in ng/g.

PFAS	LOD	LOQ	MW5 9m	MW5 5.10m	MW4 2.70m	MW4 9.15m	MW5 2.90m	MW4 5m
PFBS	0.093	0.31	2.23	<LOQ	<LOQ	2.86	<LOQ	<LOQ
PFPeS	0.075	0.25	<LOD	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOD	0.27	<LOQ
PFHxS	0.03	0.10	<LOQ	0.62	0.36	<LOQ	2.76	0.15
PFHpS	0.12	0.40	<LOQ	<LOQ	1.65	<LOD	1.59	1.34
PFOS	0.111	0.37	<LOQ	<LOQ	17.80	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
FOSA	0.24	0.80	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFNS	0.267	0.89	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFDS	0.18	0.60	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFDoS	0.327	1.09	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFBA	0.423	1.41	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
PFPeA	0.15	0.50	<LOD	0.73	2.16	0.53	1.69	1.04
PFHxA	0.159	0.53	<LOQ	0.93	1.79	<LOQ	1.84	0.64
PFHpA	0.108	0.36	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.54	<LOQ	0.95	<LOQ
PFOA	0.066	0.22	1.00	0.93	2.03	0.76	3.76	<LOQ
PFNA	0.039	0.13	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.59	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
PFDA	0.417	1.39	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
PFUnA	0.363	1.21	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOD	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
PFDoA	0.504	1.68	<LOD	<LOD	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOQ	<LOD
PFTTrDA	0.504	1.68	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFTeDA	0.432	1.44	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFHxDA	0.624	2.08	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
PFODA	1.488	4.96	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
6:2FTSA/ H4-PFOS	0.3	1.00	<LOQ	2.47	6.33	<LOQ	3.98	<LOQ
Sum PFAS (ng/g) ²			3.23	5.68	33.25	4.15	16.84	3.17

² Target method for PFAS including 41 substances

Figure 5 : Geological profile from Site 2 and PFAS fingerprint in soil from MW5

4 Methodology

4.1 Flow scheme for best technology selection to be applied in-situ

The designed workflow for choosing the technology that was tested in the field consisted of the steps presented in Figure 6. First, a literature review was performed to select the chemicals that would be tested at lab-scale, based on the site characterization, feasibility and cost of the treatments. Once the chemicals were chosen the lab testing began. The first experiments were performed with synthetic groundwater that mimicked the groundwater from the two sites in CS#7: Site 2, with PFAS-containing groundwater, and Site 1, where there is the presence of organochlorine compounds. The agitated batch experiments consisted of evaluating the degradation of a single PFAS (Perfluorohexanoic acid, PFHxA) or organochlorine (Trichloroethylene, TCE) compound with the selected treatments, at different reagents concentrations during different periods of time (1, 2 and 5 h) at 20 °C. The second step involved choosing the two tested chemicals that gave the best results in the previous step and testing them with a combination of spiked PFAS or organochlorines with synthetic water. The next consisted of repeating some of the laboratory experiments as in step 2, but with real groundwater from both sites. From that point on, we knew which treatment was the most appropriate, at which concentration the reagents should be applied, and the necessary contact time to degrade the PFAS and organochlorines from the groundwater from the two sites.

Figure 6 : Flow scheme for best technology selection to be applied on field testing

The following steps were only performed for PFAS treatment, since the field testing was only performed at Site 2, where no organochlorines are present. Step 4 consisted of batch experiments with in-situ groundwater and soil. Since the soil also exhibits PFAS, the reagent dosage needed to be increased to treat both PFAS in groundwater and in the soil matrix. In the final step, a column experiment mimicking the field conditions was conducted to determine the required contact time to degrade pollutants in heterogeneous media, without external agitation.

Finally, based on lab-testing results, one treatment was chosen for field testing. In making this choice, PFAS degradation rates, by-products formation, reagents consumption and associated costs were considered.

4.2 Laboratory testing

4.2.1 Batch experiments with synthetic groundwater

Based on the reported results on the literature review, the selected treatments for the first set of experiments were: persulfate with different activators (Fe(II) or nZVI or Fe(VI) or nZVI and Fe(VI)), Fe(VI) and nZVI. Table 4 shows the different applied conditions and its rationale. Sodium persulfate was purchased at Sigma-Aldrich and potassium ferrate (Envifer) and nZVI (Nanofer 25DS) at Nanoiron.

Table 4 : Experimental conditions tested on first batch experiments with synthetic groundwater

Batch experiment	Spiked comp.	Water matrix	Incubation time	Reagent concentrations		Experiment reagent
				Low	High	
1	For VOC: TCE For PFAS: PFHxA	Synthetic GW	1, 2.5 and 5h	1 mM	10 mM	Ps
				1 mM	10 mM	Fe(II)
				1 mM+1 mM	10 mM + 10 mM	Ps+Fe(II)
				1 g/L	10 g/L	S-nZVI
				1 mM+1 g/L	10 mM + 10 g/L	PS+S-nZVI
				1 mM	6 mM	Fe(VI)
				1 mM+1 mM	6 mM + 6 mM for PFAS and 10 mM + 10 mM for OC	PS+Fe(VI)
				1 mM + 1 mM + 1 g/L	6 mM + 6 mM + 6 g/L for PFAS and 10 mM + 10 mM + 10 g/L for OC	PS+Fe(VI)+S-nZVI
2	For VOC: DCE, TCE and PCE. For PFAS: PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS	Synthetic GW	1, 2.5 and 5h	10 mM + 10 g/L		PS+S-nZVI
				10 mM + 10 mM + 10 g/L		PS+Fe(VI)+S-nZVI

The first agitated laboratory batch experiments (step 1 in Figure 6) consisted of evaluating the degradation at 20 °C of a single organochlorine or PFAS at initial concentration of 100 µg/L with the selected chemicals at different reagents concentrations (Table 4). The spiked organochlorine and PFAS were trichloroethylene (TCE) and perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), respectively. This choice was made based on the concentrations found on the site: TCE was the compound with higher concentration at Site 1 (8 ng/L) while PFHxA was among the most concentrated compounds (8 µg/L) in Site 2. In addition, PFHxA was chosen because it is an intermediate compound of the degradation route of 6:2 FTS, PFOS and PFHpA which were found at high concentrations in the site and thus, it allowed to assess the degradation of these recalcitrant intermediate compounds. The matrix for the first set of experiments consisted of synthetic groundwater with 1.2 mM Ca²⁺, 0.85 mM Mg²⁺, 3.23

mM Cl⁻, 0.25 mM NO₃⁻ and 0.17 mM HCO₃⁻ with pH of 7.4 and electrical conductivity of 500 µS/cm. The containers for PFAS experiments were made of HDPE while glass material was used for organochlorines.

Batch reactors were running for 1, 2 and 5 h to evaluate the kinetic removal reactions. This duration is enough to efficiently remove PFAS: it has been suggested in different reports that the efficiency in the degradation of different persistent organic pollutants and emerging contaminants significantly increase when using concentration ranges of oxidant reagent from 1 to 20 mM. Under these circumstances the degradation of some organic contaminants could take over 360 minutes (Calenciuc et al., 2022; Kang et al., 2019).

The second batch of laboratory experiments (step 2 on Figure 6) were performed in similar conditions to the first set but with a combination of spiked PFAS or VOC. The synthetic matrix in this case contained 2.2 mM Na⁺, 1.2 mM Ca²⁺, 0.82 mM Mg²⁺, 3.3 mM Cl⁻, 1.1 mM SO₄²⁻, 0.25 mM NO₃⁻ and 0.18 mM HCO₃⁻ while pH was 6.8 and the electrical conductivity 1350 µS/cm. For PFAS, the spiked compounds were 100 µg/L of PFPeA, 10 µg/L of PFHxA, 5 µg/L of 6:2 FTS and 1 µg/L of PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS. For organochlorines experiments 10 µg/L of TCE, PCE, and 1,2-DCE were added to the batch reactors. These spiked concentrations are similar to those found in the field sites. The containers for PFAS were switched to glass to limit the adsorption found on HDPE in the first set of experiments.

4.2.2 Batch experiments with real groundwater

The third and fourth batches of laboratory experiments (step 3 in Figure 6) focused on testing real groundwater (GW) in triplicate, spiked with 10 µg/L of a mixture of PFAS or volatile organochlorines at different incubation times (0–5 hours and 0, 9, and 24 hours, respectively) and a high reagent concentration of PS+nZVI and PS+Fe(VI). In the fourth batch, PFAS experiments were conducted using different ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 for PS+Fe(VI), and 1:1 for PS+nZVI (Table 5). Reconsideration of the PS+nZVI treatment was needed due to the precipitation of ferric sludge in the PS+Fe(VI) combination, which could potentially pose challenges for the in-situ implementation. The characterization of the real groundwater is provided in Annex I and Annex II.

Table 5 : Experimental conditions tested on batch experiments with real groundwater

Batch experiment	Spiked comp.	Water matrix	Incubation time	Reagent concentrations	Experiment reagents
3	For VOC: DCE, TCE and PCE.	Real GW	0 and 5h	10 mM + 10 g/L	PS+S-nZVI
	For PFAS: PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS			10 mM + 10 mM	PS+Fe(VI)
4	For VOC: DCE, TCE and PCE. For PFAS: PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS	Real GW	0, 9 and 24h	10 mM + 10 g/L	PS+S-nZVI
	For PFAS: PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS			10 mM + 10 Mm and 10 mM + 20 Mm	PS+Fe(VI)

4.2.3 Batch experiments with real groundwater and soil

The fifth batch of experiments (step 4 in Figure 6) focused on testing real GW and soil from CS#7. These experiments were conducted exclusively with PFAS, as field testing will only be performed at Site 2, where no organochlorines are present. The experiments used a soil-to-water ratio of 1:2, with the same reagent concentrations as in the fourth set, but with extended reaction times of 48 and 91 hours. After the reaction time, the samples were centrifuged to separate the solid and liquid phases. Once separated, an internal standard was added. The soil characterization is provided in Annex III.

Table 6 : Experimental conditions tested on batch experiments with real groundwater and soil (only for PFAS)

Batch experiment	Spiked comp.	Matrix	Incubation time	Reagent concentrations	Experiment reagents
5	PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS	Real GW and soil, ratio 2:1	0, 48 and 91h	10 mM + 10 g/L	PS+S-nZVI
				10 mM + 10 Mm and 10 mM + 20 Mm	PS+Fe(VI)

4.2.4 Column experiments

The final set of laboratory experiments involved column tests using soil and groundwater from CS#7 Site 2 spiked with 10 µg/L of a PFAS mixture. This experiment was performed using real GW and soil were performed only for the PFAS-polluted site. Two separate experiments were performed: one using a 1:1 ratio of PS+Fe(VI) and the other a 1:1 ratio of PS+nZVI. The decision to use a 1:1 ratio of

Fe(VI) was made based on the PFAS removal results observed during the fifth batch of experiments with real GW and soil. Despite the less effective PFAS removal results observed with nZVI in the fifth batch, it was still included in the column experiments to evaluate its potential, considering the higher soil proportion that might improve treatment efficacy. Two punctual reagent injection were performed. The experiment began with the injection of PFAS-spiked groundwater, followed by punctual injection of approximately 200 mL of reagent solution over 20 minutes. After the reagent injection, PFAS-spiked groundwater was again continuously injected. Eluent samples were collected at the column outlet, with 12 samples per column taken at different times (see Table 7). At the end of the experiment, two soil samples were collected from each column—one near the inlet and one near the outlet—to evaluate potential adsorption in the soil.

Figure 7 : Experimental layout for the column test.

Table 7 : Experimental conditions tested on column experiments with real groundwater and soil (only for PFAS).

Column experiment	Spiked comp.	Matrix	Sampling time	Reagent concentrations	Experiment reagent
1	PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS	Real GW and soil	0, 2, 8, 21, 46, 52, 61, 92, 111, 124, 155, 175 and 200 min	10 mM + 10 g/L	PS+S-nZVI
				10 mM + 10 Mm	PS+Fe(VI)

Before proceeding to field tests with the PS+Fe(VI) combination, which achieved higher PFAS removal, additional experiments were conducted to optimize the Fe(VI) ratio. The goal was to reduce ferrate usage, thereby minimizing alkalinity while maintaining the same PFAS removal efficiency as observed in the fifth batch of experiments. Two tests were conducted: one with groundwater and the other with groundwater and soil, using two different ratios of ferrate (VI): 10 mM PS + 1 mM Fe(VI) and 10 mM PS + 0.1 mM Fe(VI). pH, redox potential, and PFAS concentration were monitored throughout the experiments.

4.2.5 Ultrasonic cavitation

Sonochemical-based treatment has emerged as a promising technique for PFAS removal, leveraging acoustic cavitation to generate localized high temperatures and reactive species capable of breaking down these contaminants. The propagation of intense sound waves in liquids with a power ultrasound device can produce acoustic cavitation that involves the initiation of bubble growth, followed by intense collapse events. During the collapse, the enclosed energy in the cavitation bubble gets released into the surroundings while generating both sonophysical effects (microjets, microstreaming, shockwaves) and sonochemical effects (pyrolysis and radical generation) (Panda et al., 2019). High-frequency (500-1000 kHz) power ultrasound is believed to mineralize PFAS via high-temperature pyrolysis at the bubble core and at the bubble-liquid interfacial region owing to its surfactant property. The collapse event could generate temperatures up to 5000 K, which is ideal for the pyrolysis of inert compounds.

4.2.5.1 PFOS batch experiments

Before proceeding for PFAS-contaminated groundwater treatment, we have conducted sonochemical experiments on synthetic solutions for Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) at the lab scale to optimize the reaction conditions. PFOS is one of the extensively used PFAS in consumer products and industrial applications and one of the most widely studied PFAS for its removal. For the first time, an integrated ultrasonic system with real-time operational parameters monitoring capability has been used in this work. This study investigated the calorimetric yield/efficiency and electrical energy per order (E_{EO}), PFOS mineralization efficiency and the impact of other essential parameters (initial pollutant concentration, ultrasound power density, solution pH and temperature) to understand the upscaling potential. Also, the effectiveness of the low-frequency (22 kHz) treatment was compared with the high-frequency (500 kHz) treatment. The PFOS removal extent was determined by ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS) analyses. The presence of degradation by-products was also proposed based on UPLC full scan mass spectrometry analysis. The mineralization efficiency was determined by ion-chromatography (IC) analysis by measuring fluoride evolution over the treatment time.

PFOS stock solution (200 mg/L) was prepared in Milli-Q water and was stored at 2 °C for subsequent experiment needs. For sonochemical experiments, the desired working solutions of concentration range from 2 µg/L to 5 mg/L were prepared following the dilution of the stock solution in Milli-Q water. Two different bath-type reactors (500 mL) having 22 kHz and 500 kHz frequency generators were used for conducting the experiments while being operated consistently with 300 mL reaction solution capacity. The jacketed reactors are made up of stainless steel (316L) while having a height of 114.4 mm and an internal diameter of 81 mm. The maximum external diameter is 119 mm. The total cooling volume within the reactor's jacket is 197 mL. The reactor and ultrasound generator were connected to the NexTgen PC software, which is an innovative diagnosis tool for the ultrasound system. The complete set-up was custom-made by SinapTec, France. The NexTgen software makes it possible to select the operating mode of the generator (frequency and amplitude control) and to

optimize all other operating parameters (reaction solution temperature, precise stop conditions) for steering the ultrasound process. The interface allows adjusting the generators' parameters in perfect control and recording the operation data for later access of those results and traceability of the ultrasound system. Sonochemical treatments were conducted for up to 180 min and samples were collected at regular intervals for UPLC-MS/MS and IC analysis. The reaction solution temperature was maintained (25–35 °C) by a chiller having a water bath and recirculating capacity. The ultrasonic power density (200–400 W/L) and PFOS initial concentration (2 µg/L–5 mg/L) were varied to understand the optimal treatment conditions. The reaction pH was monitored continuously to understand the PFOS mineralization progress. To replicate the industrial application feasibility, all experiments were conducted under the air atmosphere rather than the argon atmosphere. Calorimetric measurements were performed to evaluate the power efficiency. To validate outcomes, individual experiments were repeated thrice.

UPLC-MS/MS analysis: PFOS samples were diluted with a 50/50 water/methanol mixture to ensure that the PFAS levels in the samples were within the calibration range (5 to 5000 ng/L). A volume of 0.44 mL of the diluted sample was transferred to a polypropylene (PP) vial/cap. Additions of 10 µL of 5% acetic acid diluted in water and 50 µL of an internal standard solution PFOS ¹³C₄ at 2 µg/L were made prior to UPLC-MS/MS analysis. 10 µL were injected onto a WATERS Acquity UPLC for separation on a BEH C18 column (2.1 mm × 100 mm, 1.7 µm). A delay C18 column was used (isolator column 50 mm × 2.1 mm, Waters) to avoid PFAS contamination from the chromatographic system. Necessary precautions such as utilizing PFAS-free storage tubes and flushing the liquid chromatography system before analyses were followed to eliminate any false positives. The UPLC separation was carried out at a column temperature of 35 °C using a gradient composed of solvent A (5 mM aqueous ammonium acetate) and solution B (methanol 5 mM ammonium acetate). The gradient expressed as changes in solvent A was as follows: 0-6.5 min, 95% to 5% A; 6.5-7.0 min, 5% A; 7.0-7.6 min, 5% to 95% A; 7.6-10 min, 95% A. The flow rate was 300 µL/min. Considering the properties of PFOS (polarity, acidity, electronegativity), negative electrospray ionization (ESI) was chosen as the ion source interface and the LC sample was analyzed with a WATERS XEVO-TQXS (triple quadrupole). The electrospray conditions were as follows: Desolvation temperature 500°C; Desolvation gas flow 1100L/h; Cone gas flow 150 L/h; Nebulizer gas flow 7 Bar; Capillary voltages -1000V. Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode was opted to quantify PFOS while considering the most abundant precursor/product ion transitions (PFOS: 499 → 80; PFOS ¹³C₄: 503 → 80), whereas, for qualifiers, the second MRM transitions (PFOS: 499 → 99; PFOS ¹³C₄: 503 → 99) were considered. The primary MRM transitions were used for the quantification, while the secondary transitions were used for the ion ratio confirmation to eliminate false positive results. The parameters of the MS segment were as follows: Cone voltage: 30V and Collision energy: 37eV. A good signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) was obtained after following essential precautions to avoid unwanted background contamination. Quantification was carried out by internal calibration using PFOS ¹³C₄. PFAS quantification was based on 9-point calibration curves (5 to 5000 ng/L) having R² > 0.99. In these conditions, LQ was estimated to be 20 ng/L (without considering sample dilution). Due to sample dilutions, the limit of quantification for

PFOS in samples was 10 µg/L. For the detection of by-products, analysis in full scan mode (ESI+/- 50 to 600 m/z) was performed, using the same UPLC and mass spec parameters.

IC analysis: The fluoride anion (F⁻) concentration was determined via suppressed conductivity ion chromatography with a Metrohm IC-940 system (Herisau, Switzerland). The chromatography system was fitted with a Metrohm Metrosep A Supp 7 analytical column (4 × 250 mm i.d.) and Metrosep C Trap1 guard column (4 × 30 mm i.d.). The IC separation was carried at 45 °C and the eluent consisted of 3.6 mmol/L sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃). The flow rate was 0.8 mL/min and the run time was 10 min.

4.2.5.2 AFFF and PFAS-contaminated groundwater batch experiments

AFFF stock solution (100 mg/L) were prepared using Milli-Q water and stored at 2 °C for subsequent experiments. For sonochemical treatment, AFFF working solutions (2 µg/L) were prepared by diluting the stock solution in Milli-Q water. Experiments for both AFFF and groundwater samples (300 mL reaction solutions) were carried out in bath-type reactor (500 mL capacity), equipped with 500 kHz frequency generator. Sonochemical treatments were conducted for 240 minutes for all types of samples, with samples withdrawn at regular intervals for UPLC-MS/MS analysis. The reaction solution temperature was kept constant at 25°C using a chiller with a water bath and recirculation system. Ultrasonic power density was maintained at 333 W/L. All experiments were conducted in an air atmosphere and repeated three times to ensure result reliability.

4.3 ISCO field testing

4.3.1 Tracer test

A tracer is defined as any substance or energy carried by groundwater that provides information about the direction and velocity of water movement, and consequently, the transport of potential contaminants. Tracer techniques allow for the determination of hydraulic parameters and hydrogeological connections within aquifers, as well as insights into solute transport. However, these techniques do not provide additional information on permeability, porosity, dispersivity, retardation, chemical distribution coefficients, etc.

The selected tracer should have conservative behaviour, moving at the same velocity as the water, without altering its physicochemical properties or those of the aquifer (hydrochemical interaction). It should be non-toxic, soluble, easy to detect, and cost-effective.

Various tracer test techniques exist. In this study, an instantaneous injection and/or natural parallel flow dilution test was designed. This involved introducing a mass of saline water into an upstream well and monitoring both the injection point and surrounding observation wells using conductivity measurement equipment.

The tracer test conducted at Site 2 took place in May 2024. A pulse injection of 200 L of water was performed at point MW1 over a period of 35 minutes. The injected water had a high salinity of 77

mS/cm. Monitoring was carried out at the control piezometer network located downstream (MW2 and MW5) and surrounding (MW4) the injection point. The observation points were at varying distances from the injection point, with MW2 being the closest at 4 meters and MW4 the farthest at 20 meters. Downstream monitoring at MW2 and MW5 was conducted using installed CTD conductivity sensors.

In an instantaneous injection, the breakthrough curve represents the variation in mean concentration over time. Alternatively, it can be expressed as the recovered mass ratio (Total Recovered Mass/Injected Mass) as a function of time (see Figure 7 and Figure 8).

Figure 8 : Recovered mass breakthrough curve over time at point MW-2.

Figure 9 : Recovered mass breakthrough curve over time at point MW-5.

From this curve, we can determine the mean arrival time of the tracer (t_0 , also referred to as the advective transit time). Additionally, we can calculate the real flow velocity, which is given by:

$$v = \frac{q}{\phi} \text{ and } v = \frac{R}{t_0} \text{ or } v = \frac{L}{t_0}$$

By manipulating these formulas, we can derive an expression that allows us to estimate the porosity (ϕ):

$$v = \frac{k * i}{\phi} = \frac{R}{t_0} \Rightarrow \phi = \frac{k * i * t_0}{R}$$

On the other hand, the dispersion coefficient D is given by the following expression:

$$D = \frac{\sigma_t^2 \cdot v}{2t_0}$$

And dispersivity (α) by:

$$\alpha = \frac{D}{v} = \frac{\sigma_t^2 \cdot v}{2t_0}$$

4.3.2 In situ remediation

The in-situ oxidation involved the application of an oxidizing agent in the saturated zone of the subsurface, carried out in three separate injections spaced 15 days apart. The purpose of the test was to evaluate the efficiency of the treatment through the oxidation of PFAS compounds present in groundwater.

In this case, the oxidizing agent used was sodium persulfate, activated by the alkalization of the medium using a siliceous base. The concentrations of the oxidizing agent in the injected water mass were increased in the second campaign of injections to estimate the effective range of the oxidant in the subsurface. In all cases, the injected mass consisted of 200 L of water with the dissolved oxidant, which was applied at MW1 (see Figure 10). Concentration of the oxidant was, according to the results obtained at lab-scale and detailed in the present report, 10 mM PS activated with 1 mM of Fe (VI) during the first set of injections (3×200 L), and 30 mM PS with 3 mM Fe (VI) during the second set of injections (3×200 L). The oxidant/pollutant ratios observed during the pilot test were 36 and 164 (concentration oxidant/concentration pollutant) for the first and second set of injections, respectively. The preparation of the oxidant solution was carried out using a homogenizing tank, and the injection was performed using a well-sealing system and a low-pressure pneumatic pump (<1 bar).

Figure 10 : In-situ remediation layout

During the test, the concentrations of chemical contaminants and the main geochemical parameters of the subsurface were monitored at the injection point and the surrounding control points to assess the feasibility and estimate the efficiency of the treatment.

Below is the monitoring of the ISCO (In Situ Chemical Oxidation) test conducted in the groundwater of the study area:

Table 8 : Monitoring of the chemical oxidation test in the saturated zone.

Injection Point	Control Points	Parameters
MW1	MW2 and MW5	<u>In situ parameters:</u> physicochemical (pH, T, CE, OD and Eh) and groundwater level <u>Analysis:</u> PFAS and toxicological assays

4.4 Analysis of chlorinated solvents

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in groundwater from Site 1 (Figure 2) were analyzed by IDAEA-CSIC using a Purge-and-Trap (PT) technique coupled with gas chromatography (GC) with a mass spectrometer (MS) instrument. The PT manually dispensed 10 mL of the water sample or a standard solution. The samples placed in the vial were purged for 11 min by a stream of helium at 40 mL/min and trapped in an adsorbent. After desorption at 250 °C for 4 min, the volatile organic compounds were transferred directly into a Trace GC coupled to a MS equipped with a CP-Select 624 CB capillary column (60 m x 250 µm x 1.4 µm). The column was set at 40 °C during 10 min, ramped 50–150 °C at 5 °C/min, and to 210 °C at 15 °C/min, this temperature was held for 10 min. The injector was operated in split mode and helium was used as carrier gas.

The MS was operated in full-scan acquisition mode in the m/z 35-380 Da range. Quantification was performed by the internal calibration method using fluorobenzene, 4-bromofluorobenzene and 1,2-dichloroethane-d4 as internal standards. Nine-point calibration curves were prepared using deionized water just before instrumental analysis.

The following 59 VOCs were determined in groundwater samples: dichlorodifluoromethane, chloromethane, vinyl chloride, bromomethane, chloroethane, trichlorofluoromethane, 1,1-dichloroethylene, methylene chloride, trans-1,2-dichloroethylene, 1,1-dichloroethane, 2,2-dichloropropane, cis-1,2-dichloroethylene, bromochloromethane, chloroform, 1,1,1-trichloroethane, carbon tetrachloride, 1,1-dichloropropylene, benzene, 1,2-dichloroethane, trichloroethylene, 1,2-dichloropropane, dibromomethane, bromodichloromethane, cis-1,3-dichloropropylene, toluene, trans-1,3-dichloropropylene, 1,1,2-trichloroethane, tetrachloroethylene, 1,3-dichloropropane, dibromochloromethane, 1,2-dibromoethane, chlorobenzene, 1,1,1,2-tetrachloroethane, ethylbenzene, m-xylene/p-xylene, o-xylene, styrene, bromoform, isopropylbenzene, bromobenzene, 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane, 1,2,3-trichloropropane, n-propylbenzene, 2-chlorotoluene, 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene, 4-chlorotoluene, tert-butylbenzene, 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene, sec-butylbenzene, 1,3-dichlorobenzene, 4-isopropyltoluene, 1,4-dichlorobenzene, n-butylbenzene, 1,2-dichlorobenzene, 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene, hexachlorobutadiene, naphthalene, 1,2,3-trichlorobenzene.

The quantification of DCE, TCE, and PCE's removal in the water samples from the first three experimental batches was conducted as described in Table 4 and Table 5. Water samples were collected in 20 mL amber vials to a volume of 3 mL, along with NaCl (250 mg), for headspace SPME analysis using a TriPlus 500 headspace sampler. The solutions were agitated for 20 min at 40 °C. The optimum sampling conditions were as follows: incubation time, 5 min; incubation temperature, 40 °C; extraction time, 15 min; extraction temperature, 40 °C; stirring speed, 700 rpm; desorption time, 10 min; desorption temperature, 260 °C. The microextractions were performed using a manual solid-phase microextraction fibre assembly fitted with an 85 µm carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (85-CAR/PDMS) fibre and a fibre coated with a 7 µm thickness film of PDMS (7 µm PDMS) for the first, second, and third experiments' samples, respectively. When new, both fibres were conditioned for 30 min in a GC injector port at 300 °C before analysis.

A Trace GC Ultra gas chromatograph, coupled to a Nitrogen Phosphorus Detector and Electron Capture Detector Trace (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), was used for analytical separation and detection. The chromatographic column was a 60 m × 0.25 mm × 1.4 µm DB-624 column (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow of 1.0 mL/min; and the inlet temperature was 260 °C. The oven temperature gradually increased from 40 to 280 °C. The splitless time was 0.8 min and the detector temperature was 300 °C. The limits of detection and quantification are detailed in Table 9.

The identification and quantification of the chlorinated solvents and vinyl chloride in the water samples from Batch 4 were performed using a PT-GC-MS instrument, as described in the analytical methodology for the monitoring previously mentioned.

Table 9 : Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) of OCs analysed for both analytical methodologies: Purge-and-Trap (PT) coupled with gas chromatography (GC) with a mass spectrometer (MS) instrument and headspace solid-phase microextraction gas chromatography electron capture detector (SPME-GC-ECD). All values are expressed in µg/L.

Compound	PT-GC-MS		SPME-GC-ECD	
	LOD	LOQ	LOD	LOQ
dichlorodifluoromethane	0.026	0.088		
chloromethane	0.053	0.177		
vinyl chloride	0.038	0.125		
bromomethane	0.174	0.580		
chloroethane	0.261	0.870		
trichlorofluoromethane	0.046	0.155		
1,1-dichloroethylene	0.044	0.148		
methylene chloride	1.911	6.371		
trans-1,2-dichloroethylene	0.055	0.182		
1,1-dichloroethane	0.015	0.049		
2,2-dichloropropane	0.006	0.021		
cis-1,2-dichloroethylene	0.012	0.041	0.039	0.130
bromochloromethane	0.011	0.038		
chloroform	0.090	0.300		
1,1,1-trichloroethane	0.006	0.020		
carbon tetrachloride	0.017	0.057		
1,1-dichloropropylene	0.021	0.069		
benzene	0.011	0.036		
1,2-dichloroethane	0.030	0.099		
trichloroethylene	0.020	0.065	0.003	0.010
1,2-dichloropropane	0.015	0.049		
dibromomethane	0.007	0.022		
bromodichloromethane	0.004	0.012		
cis-1,3-dichloropropylene	0.007	0.023		
toluene	0.059	0.196		
trans-1,3-dichloropropylene	0.008	0.027		
1,1,2-trichloroethane	0.006	0.019		
tetrachloroethylene	0.046	0.153	0.024	0.080
1,3-dichloropropane	0.003	0.009		
dibromochloromethane	0.023	0.076		
1,2-dibromoethane	0.011	0.035		
chlorobenzene	0.006	0.021		
1,1,1,2-tetrachloroethane	0.002	0.005		
ethylbenzene	0.004	0.014		
m-xylene/p-xylene	0.004	0.012		
o-xylene	0.003	0.010		
styrene	0.003	0.008		
bromoform	0.024	0.081		

	PT-GC-MS		SPME-GC-ECD	
isopropylbenzene	0.003	0.009		
bromobenzene	0.004	0.012		
1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane	0.004	0.014		
1,2,3-trichloropropane	0.003	0.009		
n-propylbenzene	0.005	0.018		
2-chlorotoluene	0.004	0.012		
1,3,5-trimethylbenzene	0.004	0.015		
4-chlorotoluene	0.005	0.018		
tert-butylbenzene	0.003	0.011		
1,2,4-trimethylbenzene	0.004	0.013		
sec-butylbenzene	0.006	0.021		
1,3-dichlorobenzene	0.006	0.021		
4-isopropyltoluene	0.006	0.020		
1,4-dichlorobenzene	0.007	0.024		
n-butylbenzene	0.011	0.038		
1,2-dichlorobenzene	0.003	0.010		
1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane	0.049	0.164		
1,2,4-trichlorobenzene	0.013	0.042		
hexachlorobutadiene	0.035	0.115		
naphthalene	0.011	0.037		
1,2,3-trichlorobenzene	0.014	0.047		

4.5 Analysis of PFAS

PFAS-contaminated water samples from Site 2 (lab scale and field testing) were analyzed by IDAEA-CSIC according to the protocol described in Deliverable 1.4 from WP1. The workflow that the group followed includes the assessment of the presence of PFAS (legacy and emerging compounds) in waters. The method is based on off-line solid phase extraction with Oasis WAX 3cc for the extraction of 200 mL (in triplicates) after spiking of internal standard compounds. Afterwards, the extracts have been analysed by liquid chromatography coupled to high resolution mass spectrometry that has allowed the target and the suspect screening of PFASs related compounds. The list of compounds and limits of quantification are detailed in the next Table 10.

Table 10 : LOQ for PFAS with an initial amount 200 ml of water

#compd		LOQ (ng/L)
Carboxylic acids		
1	PFBA	3.52
2	PFPeA	0.15
3	PFHxA	0.38
4	PFHpA	0.40
5	PFOA	0.55
6	PFNA	0.31
7	PFDA	3.47
8	PFUnA	3.01
9	PFDoA	4.20
10	PFTTrDA	4.20
11	PFTeDA	8.10
12	PFHxDA	5.20
13	PFODA	12.40
Sulfonic acids & sulfonamides		
14	PFBS	0.76
15	PFPeS	0.76
16	PFHxS	0.77
17	PFHpS	0.99
18	PFOS	0.91
19	PFNS	2.24
20	PFDS	1.50
21	PFDoS	5.00
22	FOSA	1.00
Fluorotelomer sulfonic acids		
23	4:2 FTSA	1.00
24	6:2 FTSA	1.00
25	8:2 FTSA	1.00
26	10:2 FTSA	2.00
New PFAS		
27	6:2 diPAP	0.50
28	8:2 diPAP	2.50
29	ADONA	1.25
30	EtFOSA	0.50
31	EtFOSAA	0.50
32	FOSAA	0.50
33	MeFOSAA	0.50
34	MeFOSA	0.50
35	HFPO-DA (Gen-X)	1.25
36	PFMOAA	0.50
37	PFMOPrA	2.50
38	PFMOBA	2.50
39	PFO ₂ HxA	0.50
40	PFO ₃ OA	0.50
41	PFO ₄ DA	2.50

4.6 Toxicological assays

For each of the samples taken for toxicological assays during the field testing described in 4.3.2, PFAS were extracted by means of solid-phase extraction (SPE) on a weak-anion-exchange cartridge (WAX-SPE). After conditioning the WAX-SPE cartridge with subsequently MeOH:0.1% NH₄OH, MeOH and ultra-pure water, the samples were loaded on the columns and washed with NH₄AC (pH4) and THF:MeOH (75:25) (v/v). Finally, PFAS were eluted with MeOH:0.1% NH₄OH and collected in tubes containing ENVI-Carb. Following vortexing (10 sec.), the eluates were centrifuged (10 minutes at 1800 g) and collected supernatants were evaporated under a gentle flow of N₂. The final extracts were reconstituted in 30 µL of DMSO and serial dilution in DMSO were prepared with log increments of 0.5 (1, 3, 10, 30 and 100-times dilutions). Then these were analysed for their potential to disrupt with T₄-TTR binding (PFAS CALUX), ER α -receptor activation (ER α CALUX), PXR-receptor activation (PXR CALUX), cytotoxicity (Cytotox CALUX), AR-receptor antagonism (anti-AR CALUX), and PPAR γ -receptor antagonism (anti-PPAR γ CALUX).

TTR-Binding Assay. Serial sample dilutions were incubated overnight at 4°C in Tris-buffer (pH 8.0) with TTR (0.058 µM) and a fixed concentration of T₄ (0.052 µM) (3.2% of the sample dilution in the incubation mixture). After incubation, TTR-bound and free T₄ were separated using a Bio-Gel P-6DG column. The eluate was then transferred into the assay medium, and TR β CALUX cells were exposed for 24 hours.

CALUX Bioassays. CALUX cells were seeded in 96-well plates with assay medium. After exposing the CALUX cells to serial sample dilutions in triplicate (PFAS CALUX: dilutions after TTR-binding assay; other CALUX: dilution series of sample extracts), the induction of luciferase production was measured by luminescence using a Berthold luminometer following the addition of luciferin substrate. On each 96-well plate, complete calibration curves for each bioassay are also analysed using the relevant reference compounds.

Data analysis. The analysis results of sample extracts, presented as induction relative to the standard reference compound, were interpolated into the calibration curves of each respective bioassay for quantitative assessment of disruptive potential. This process was carried out using the statistical software package GraphPad Prism V5.03. Only dilutions without any signs of cytotoxicity were considered for the final evaluation of the analysis. All findings are expressed as the equivalent amount of reference compound per liter of processed water.

5 Results

5.1 Literature review and chemical selection for the in-situ remediation

The literature review was performed based on the characterization of sites and pollutants and with the aim of finding the most efficient treatment at the lowest cost, to the best of our knowledge. In this regard, it was decided that the implemented strategy at full scale would consist of an in-situ treatment with an injection of chemicals. Therefore, some treatments such as photocatalytic reduction were discarded because they cannot be applied as an in-situ treatment and because of its operational costs.

Based on this premise, a list of possible treatments that could be applied was produced. One of the most promising treatments was persulfate activated with different catalysts as it has widespread application for groundwater remediation via In-Situ Chemical Oxidation (ISCO) (Petri et al., 2011). Persulfate (PS) is a strong oxidant that in combination with different activators (transition metals, temperature, ultraviolet, etc.) can degrade a wide variety of organic pollutants. Another possible choice was ferrate (Fe(VI)) that is also a strong oxidant that has been shown to be effective in removing organic pollutants from water (Sharma et al., 2016), without the requirement of an activator. A third option was the employment of nano zero-valent iron (nZVI) which is a strong reductant that has shown good results in degrading a wide variety of halogenated organic compounds, among others (Li et al., 2021) and it also has reported to work with PFAS (Zhang et al., 2018). Besides, the synergistic effect of the combination of these different reagents has been shown to be more effective than the reagents alone in some cases (Deng et al., 2020). Table 11 and Table 12 show the literature review with the mentioned chemical reagents and its reported removal yield with respect to some organochlorines and PFAS that are present in CS#7.

Table 11 : Literature review about chlorinated solvents removal efficiency with the proposed chemical treatments

Treatment	Contaminant	Removal	Type of experiment	pH	Temperature	Type of water	Reference
Fe(VI)	TCE	In ultrapure water at pH 7 : 97%, In real water with dissolved organic carbon at pH 7 : 42%	Batch experiments with 10 mL containing solution in 20 mL septum sealed vials. Duration:30 min	Initial pH 3, 5, 7, 9 or 11	Not reported	Ultrapure water or real groundwater spiked with 0.1-10 mg/L of TCE and with Fe(VI) at 50 mg/L	Dobosy et al. (2016)
nZVI	TCE, PCE, DCE	Generally <80% depending on the pilot test and on the type of employed nZVI	Full-scale experiments	Real conditions	Real condition	Real water	Galdames et al. (2020). Review
Persulfate	TCE	< 30% removal	Batch experiments in 40 mL septum sealed vials, duration: 16 h	Final pH 6.2	20 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 50 or 375 mg/L TCE and a molar ratio of TCE: Persulfate of 1:20	Al-Shamsi and Thomson (2013)
Persulfate activated with nZVI	TCE	> 95% removal	Batch experiments in 40 mL septum sealed vials, duration: 16 h	Final pH 2.6	20 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 50 or 375 mg/L TCE and a molar ratio of TCE: Persulfate: nZVI of 1:20:150	Al-Shamsi and Thomson (2013)
Persulfate activated with Fe(II)	TCE	Nearly 100% removal	Batch experiments in 60 mL glass reactors, duration: 1 h	Final pH around 3	20 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 60 mg/L TCE and a molar ratio of Persulfate:Chelate:Fe(II):TCE molar ratio of 20:2:10:1	Liang et al. (2004)
	PCE	Complete removal	Batch experiments in 250 mL glass reactors, duration: 30 min	Initial pH of 3	20 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 0.015 mmol/L PCE and a molar ratio of Persulfate:Fe(II):Hydroxylamine:PCE molar ratio of 30:4:20:1	Wu et al. (2016)

Table 12 : Literature review about PFAS removal efficiency with the proposed chemical treatments

Treatment	Contaminant	Removal	Type of experiment	pH	Temperature	Type of matrix	Intermediate compounds	Reference
Fe(II)	PFOA	no removal	Anoxic batch reactors in 15 mL PP tubes, duration: 4 h	7	Ambient temperature	Synthetic water spiked with 680 µg/L of PFOA	No degradation	Tran et al. (2021)
Fe (VI)	PFHxS	~50%	Ball milling in 40 mL containers with PFHxS salt (1 g) and solid reagents (1.4 g) for 4 h	NA	Not reported	Solid phase	Formation of intermediate compounds that were degraded to some extent, as indicated by defluorination (~35%)	Deng et al. (2020)
	PFOA PFOS	PFOA: 10% at pH 7 PFOS: 18% at pH 7 Lower at pH 9. Other ferrates Fe(V) and Fe(IV) exhibited removals up to ~30%	Batch experiments in 1 L HDPE bottles, duration: 5 days	Initial pH of 7 and 9	Not reported	Synthetic water spiked with 4.5-7 mg/L PFOA and 0.8-1.3 mg/L PFOS at pH 7 and 9.	Not assessed	Yates et al. (2014)
Fe(VI) + nZVI	PFHxS	~100%	Ball milling in 40 mL containers with PFHxS salt (1 g) and solid reagents (1.4 g) for 4 h	NA	40-60 °C	Solid phase	Formation of intermediate compounds that were almost completely degraded, as indicated by defluorination (~95%)	Deng et al. (2020)
nZVI	PFOS	No removal at any temperature or initial pH	Batch experiments in 20 mL PP vials, duration: 3 h	Initial pH of 3, 7 and 9	20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 10 mg/L PFOS and 0.5 g/L ZVI	No degradation	Parenty et al. (2020)
	PFHxS	~85%	Ball milling in 40 mL containers with PFHxS salt (1 g) and solid reagents (1.4 g) for 4 h	NA	Not reported	Solid phase	Formation of intermediate compounds that were degraded to some extent, as indicated by defluorination (~30%)	Deng et al. (2020)
	PFOA, PFNA, PFOS, PFDA	Commercial nZVI <27% removal at 1 h Synthetized MgAC coated nZVI 38-96% removal at 1 h	Batch experiments in 80 mL reactors, duration: 24 h	Initial pH of 3	20 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 200 µg/L of each fluorinated compound and 1 g/L of nZVI	No intermediates compounds detected although F- mass balance suggest that the removal was due to adsorption and to degradation	Arvaniti et al. (2015)
	PFOS, PFHxS, PFDA, PFNA, PFOA	No specific % reported.	Sorption batch experiments in 15 mL PP tubes, duration: 7 days	Equilibrium pH 8-9	22 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 1-20000 µg/L of each fluorinated compound and 0.1-1.2 g/L of nZVI	No reported transformation of PFOA or PFOS. No information reported for the rest of PFAS. Removal was attributed to sorption.	Zhang et al. (2018)
Persulfate (20 °C)	PFOS	No removal at any temperature or initial pH	Batch experiments in 20 mL PP vials, duration: 3 h	Initial pH of	20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 10 mg/L PFOS and 0.3 M persulfate	No degradation	Parenty et al. (2020)

Treatment	Contaminant	Removal	Type of experiment	pH	Temperature	Type of matrix	Intermediate compounds	Reference
				3, 7 and 9				
	PFOA	No removal	Anoxic batch reactors in 15 mL PP tubes, duration: 4 h	7	Ambient temperature	Synthetic water spiked with 680 µg/L of PFOA	No degradation	Tran et al. (2021)
Persulfate activated with Fe(II)	PFOA	64%	Anoxic batch reactors in 15 mL PP tubes, duration: 4 h	Initial pH 7- final pH 2.4	Ambient temperature	Synthetic water spiked with 680 µg/L of PFOA	Not assessed	Tran et al. (2021)
	PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS	Little to no oxidative decomposition of PFAAs occurred and the under recoveries found, particularly for PFUdA and PFOS, were primarily the result of unexpectedly slow desorption	Flow-through glass column experiment with loamy sand porous media (pH 6.1). Different experimental phases: adsorption, oxidation and desorption.	Influent pH 1.9 - Effluent pH 5	Room temperature	Synthetic groundwater spiked with 2 µg/L of PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, with an inflow of ~0.3 mL/min	Probable formation of shorter chain length PFCA during oxidation phases	McKenzie et al. (2015)
Persulfate activated with nZVI	PFOS	~10% removal at 20 °C at initial pH of 3, ~50% removal at 60 °C at initial pH of 3 Higher removal at pH 3 than 7 or 9	Batch experiments in 20 mL PP vials, duration: 3 h	Initial pH of 3, 7 and 9	20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C	Synthetic water spiked with 10 mg/L PFOS and 0.5 g/L ZVI and 0.3 M persulfate	No intermediates detected; removal attributed to adsorption onto iron oxides	Parenty et al. (2020)

5.2 Laboratory testing

Laboratory testing was performed in order to select the best oxidant combination to degrade VOC and PFAS, from Site 1 and Site 2, respectively, in order to further test it at field scale. Ultrasonic cavitation was tested at lab-scale with groundwater from Site 2.

5.2.1 Laboratory testing for chlorinated solvent polluted groundwater

5.2.1.1 Batch experiments with synthetic groundwater

Based on Site 1 characterization, TCE was selected for the first batch of remediation experiments due to its high concentration (Annex I) and its role as an indicator of chlorinated solvent pollution in GW (Balderacchi et al., 2014). Figure 11 shows that removal efficiencies varied with oxidant concentration, with zero oxidant agent showing the lowest TCE eliminations. The removal observed in the 0 mM reactor may be attributed to TCE's volatilization within the reactors, with a range spanning from 1 to 25%, as previously reported elsewhere (Liang et al., 2004). Higher oxidant concentrations (10 mM) resulted in higher removal efficiencies. Moreover, longer incubation times increased TCE removal rates, reaching its highest elimination rate at 5 h. Focusing on treatment effectiveness, reagent combinations proved more effective than using a single reagent alone. PS and Fe(II) individually showed lower efficiency, while S-nZVI and Fe(VI) had the least impact when used separately. The two combinations of chemical reagents that generated the highest removals and had statistically significant differences from the others were PS + S-nZVI and PS + Fe(VI) + S-nZVI at 10 mM reagent concentrations (92–99% removal). Based on the already-stated results, these two treatments were selected for the next experiment.

Figure 11 : Comparison of eight novel treatment methods for the removal of TCE spiked with 100 µg/L in synthetic GW (Batch 1). Various concentrations of PS, Fe(II), and Fe(VI) (0, 1, and 10 mM) and S-nZVI (0, 1, and 10 g/L) were tested (Control, Low, and High, respectively) at different times (1, 2.5, and 5 h).

In the second experiment (Batch 2), synthetic GW was spiked with DCE, TCE, and PCE at 10 µg/L each and treated with the two best oxidant combinations: PS + S-nZVI and Fe(VI) + PS + S-nZVI, both at 10 mM. Figure 10 shows that PS + S-nZVI combination achieved higher removal efficiencies (59–90%)

compared to Fe(VI) + PS + S-nZVI (48–74%), with significant differences observed only for DCE removal. The removal of chlorinated solvents was compound-dependent, with DCE (89%) and TCE (87%) removed more effectively than PCE (59%). The removal efficiencies for TCE in this batch were lower compared to previous assays using the same combinations of oxidation agents (Figure 11). This can be explained due to the lower initial concentration (concentration was reduced from 100 to 10 µg/L), but also by the presence of additional chlorinated solvents. Notably, PCE is often dechlorinated into TCE (Pierri, 2021) and DCE (Li et al., 2021), which might explain the reduced TCE removal. Unfortunately, although sorption to zero-valent iron of chlorinated solvents is also a reported reduction process alongside oxidation (Dries, et. al., 2004), in this study, we cannot distinguish between the two processes as chloride levels were not monitored.

Figure 12 : Removal efficiencies of chlorinated solvents (DCE, TCE, and PCE) in GW exposed for different times (0, 1, 2.5, and 5 h) and the best preselected oxidation treatments, at 10 mM, with each compound spiked at 10 µg/L (Batch 2).

5.2.1.2 Batch experiments with real groundwater

Since the combination of PS + S-nZVI was identified as the most effective treatment for chlorinated solvent attenuation in synthetic groundwater (GW), it was tested on real GW at 0 and 5 hours of reaction time, with 10 µg/L of three selected chlorinated solvents. As shown in Figure 13, the PS + S-nZVI treatment partially removed the chlorinated solvents after 5 hours, with removal efficiencies ranging from 50% to 99%. However, the effectiveness was compound-dependent: while TCE elimination reached 99%, DCE and PCE removals were 50% and 58%, respectively. Compared to the

previous experiment with synthetic GW, the removal of TCE and PCE was higher and similar, respectively (87% and 59%), but DCE removal was lower (50% vs. 89%). This decrease may be attributed to the matrix effect, as the real GW contained more total organic carbon (TOC) than the synthetic GW (3 mg/L vs. <1 mg/L), potentially reducing treatment efficiency as reported elsewhere due to the scavenger effect of organic matter (Dobosy et al., 2016). Thus, longer exposure times were necessary for the real GW matrix. In addition, 5-hour reactions with unspiked GW showed significant removal of chlorinated solvents at low concentrations. As depicted in Figure 4, TCE and PCE removals were around 73% and 94%, respectively. Since DCE was not detected in the unspiked GW samples, no elimination was reported for this compound.

Figure 13 : Removal of chlorinated solvents (DCE, TCE, and PCE) by a PS + S-nZVI treatment after 5 h in spiked (10 µg/L each compound) and unspiked real Site 1 GW and 10 mM of oxidant (Batch 3). N.R.=No removal.

Figure 13 shows that, with longer incubation times (9 and 24 hours), chlorinated solvent removal consistently increased, reaching 69% for DCE and 92% for PCE after 24 hours. TCE achieved 99% removal at 9 hours, with no statistically significant differences thereafter. These findings indicate a progressive increase in DCE and PCE removal with the PS + S-nZVI treatment from 9 hours (38% and 85%) to 24 hours (69% and 92%), exceeding the removal observed at 5 hours. These results suggest that extending the incubation time beyond 24 hours (e.g., two days, five days, one week) may lead to the complete removal of chlorinated solvents in real GW using this combination of oxidation agents. To ensure the safety of the process, vinyl chloride, a highly toxic byproduct of TCE oxidation, was analysed. Fortunately, vinyl chloride was not detected in any of the samples.

Figure 14 : Removal of chlorinated solvents by PS + S-nZVI treatment at 0, 9, and 24 h of incubation in real Site 1 GW spiked with 10 µg/L of each of the selected compounds (DCE, TCE, and PCE) and 10 mM of oxidant (Batch 4).

5.2.1.3 Conclusions for chlorinated solvent polluted groundwater

The study concluded that the PS and S-nZVI combination treatment, combined with high concentrations of oxidizing agent (10 mM) and longer incubation times (5 h), yielded the best results in synthetic groundwater. This approach achieved removal rates of 89% for DCE, 87% for TCE, and 59% for PCE. However, when tested with real groundwater containing 10 µg/L of each of the selected compounds, its performance decreased significantly (to 50, 99, and 58%, respectively). This suggests the need for longer incubation times for the effective treatment of real groundwater. The application of this combined approach with real, unspiked groundwater showed removal rates of 94% for TCE and 73% for PCE over a 5 h period, demonstrating its effectiveness in mitigating the presence of these contaminants. In a 24 h spiked experiment, removal rates of 69, 99, and 92% were achieved for DCE, TCE, and PCE, respectively, without generating transformation products like vinyl chloride. These results indicate that longer incubation times, beyond 24 h, may be necessary for complete chlorinated solvent removal when using this oxidation agent mixture on real groundwater. Further field-scale studies are required to assess its practical effectiveness for in situ pollutant remediation. This study was published in *Water Journal* (Cano-Lopez et al., 2024, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16091241>).

5.2.2 Laboratory testing for PFAS-polluted aquifer

5.2.2.1 Batch experiments with real groundwater and soil

The results from the batch experiments, which involved testing groundwater and soil varying ratios of reagent combinations, reveal a slight elimination of PFAS when considering soil + groundwater all together. This elimination is specifically observed for PFAS with carbon chain lengths shorter than 9, that correspond to those spiked during the experiment (i.e., PFPeA, PFHxA, 6:2-FTS, PFBA, PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS) and others also present in GW and soil from Site 2 (i.e., PFPeS, Gen X, 4:2-FTS, PFHpS, PFHpA or PFBS). In total, 13 PFAS compounds C4-C8 were detected during this experiment. The

elimination of these 13 PFAS C4-C8 was the highest under the treatment with PS activated with 20 mM Fe(VI) compared to the one activated with 10 mM Fe(VI) or 10 g/L nZVI (37%, 26% and 16%, respectively), after 91 hours of the reagent application (see Figure 15).

Regarding PFAS with C chain > 8, an increase is observed after the application of all reagent combinations compared to the initial levels, though this increase is notably lower under the PS + nZVI combination (Figure 16). These C9-C13 PFAS correspond mainly to PFNA, PFDA, MeFOSA and EtFOSA, and this phenomenon is difficult to explain since the generation of long C chain PFAS is unlikely. One possibility is that these PFAS are present in the reagents applied.

Analysing the total mass of initial PFAS at the three sampling times for each treatment, the 10 mM PS + 10 mM Fe(VI) treatment showed PFAS formation at 0 and 48 hours, resulting in a mass slightly exceeding the initial amount, with only a 6% removal observed at 91 hours. For the 10 mM PS + 20 mM Fe(VI) treatment, there was a sharp decrease in mass at 0 hours, corresponding to a 21% removal, with similar removal rates maintained at both 48 and 91 hours, indicating that oxidation processes occur rapidly. The 10 mM PS + 10 g/L nZVI treatment achieved an 18% removal at 0 hours, but the mass increased at 48 hours, suggesting PFAS formation, followed by an 8% removal at 91 hours (Figure 17).

According to this experiment, the reagents with the best performance is PS activated with 20 mM of Fe(VI), which achieves 37% removal of the most abundant PFAS. However, it is not known if during the oxidation there is formation of ultra-short PFAS (< 3C). However, two main drawbacks were observed in the experiments using Fe (VI), first the formation of ferric precipitates and second the groundwater pH around 12.5-13, that could endanger the in-situ application of these reagents.

Figure 15 : Elimination of 13 short-chain PFAS (4 – 8 carbons) in groundwater and soil under 3 different types of oxidation treatment

Figure 16 : Elimination of 6 long-chain PFAS (9 – 12 carbons) in groundwater and soil under 3 different types of oxidation treatment

Figure 17 : Elimination of the sum of the total detected PFAS in groundwater and soil under 3 different types of oxidation treatment

5.2.2.2 Column experiments

Column experiments were done still comparing Fe(VI) and nZVI as PS activators, despite the above results. One of the main objectives of these column tests was to figure out if ferric precipitates might cause clogging. For this reason, nZVI was still maintained as an option to further scale-up, since no precipitates were generated when using nZVI.

Prior to the column test, a tracer test using NaCl was conducted. From these results, the hydraulic parameters for the column were obtained as is detailed in Table 13.

Table 13 : Column hydraulic parameters

Symbol	Parameter	Unit	Result
Q	Inlet flow rate	m ³ /min	0,000010
v	Velocity (Q/A·n)	m/min	0,015915
A	Cross Sectional Area Column	m ²	0,001257
K	Hydraulic conductivity	m/min	0,007958
T	Residence time = Column length/velocity	min	12,57
r	Radius column	m	0,02
L	Column length	m	0,20
n	Effective porosity	%	0,50
DI	Dispersion Coefficient (DL=v*long column/2)	m ² /min	0,002
Ld	Dispersion Length	m	0,400
l	Curvilinear coordinate direction along flow line	m	0,2
R	Retardation factor	-	
Vp	Pore volume	m ³	0,000126

The column experiments revealed a distinct reduction in PFAS from the effluent water following the two reagent injections, with a sharp decrease observed after each injection. For the column with PS activated with 10 mM Fe(VI), elimination rates ranged from 67% to 97% across all detected PFAS (Figure 18a and c) in the effluent compared to the initial concentration of spiked groundwater. Once the reagents were eluted from the column, PFAS concentrations raised again. Based on these findings, it is better to perform the second injection between 20 and 50 minutes after the first, before PFAS concentrations begin to rise again, to further enhance PFAS removal. Soil analysis indicated that sorption occurred, with PFAS concentrations higher at both the inlet and outlet compared to initial levels (i.e., blank), particularly at the inlet due to greater precipitation of iron hydroxides in this area

(Figure 18). Taken together these findings, the removal from water can be also due to the sorption of PFAS into the soil matrix.

During the column test with PS and Fe (VI), a reduction of the outlet flow rate was observed, possible due to possible ferric precipitates, even though the flow did not stop (from 4.5 to 1.4 mL/min). pH in the outlet reached a value of 11 at the end of the second injection.

For the column with PS activated with S-nZVI, while the results were less clear, a decrease in PFAS concentration was still observed after the second injection (Figure 18). This treatment achieved removal rates between 40% and 100% for all detected PFAS in groundwater. Sorption was also evident, as PFAS levels at the inlet and outlet were higher than the initial soil concentration (Figure 18). The reduction in the outlet flow rate was not that abrupt as by using Fe(VI) as activator and pH was maintained between 6 and 7.8.

These results demonstrate that the treatment with PS activated with 10 mM Fe(VI), which achieved the highest PFAS removal rates in groundwater, is the most promising option for field-scale application. Moreover, the ferric precipitates did not worsen the hydraulic conditions of the column. However, the experiments revealed slightly alkalinity conditions. To address this, additional tests were conducted to optimize the Fe(VI) ratio. The objective was to reduce ferrate usage, thereby reducing alkalinity while maintaining the PFAS removal efficiency observed in 5.2.2.1, with groundwater and soil. Two lower Fe(VI) dosages were tested: 1 mM Fe(VI) and 0.1 mM Fe(VI). The results indicated that the 10 mM PS + 1 mM Fe(VI) combination achieved a similar PFAS removal rate to using 10 or 20 mM of Fe (VI), while maintaining a pH around 9.

Figure 18 : Colum experiments results. a) and c) PFAS concentration in the effluent with 10 mM PS + 10 mM Fe(VI) (a) and 10 mM PS + 10 g/L nZVI (c) and PFAS concentration in the soil matrix at the end of the experiment under both treatments, (b) and (d).

5.2.2.3 Conclusions for PFAS polluted aquifer using ISCO

Lab-scale experiments both in batch and column demonstrated that the best option for PFAS removal from groundwater using an ISCO strategy was the use of PS activated with Fe(VI), in front of the activation with nZVI.

A dosage of 10 mM PS activated with 20 mM Fe(VI) achieved a 37% PFAS removal at ca. 90 hours after the application, making it this combination the best candidate for field application.

However, few foreseen drawbacks of this reagent combination (PS activated with Fe(VI)) for the field upscaling were observed during this lab testing, which are the following:

- Generation of ferric precipitates, though during column tests was observed that these do not cause clogging or hydraulic issues.
- Groundwater alkalinity. When the concentration of Fe (VI) was 20 mM, the pH of water + soil increased up to 13. Further experiments were performed in order to adjust Fe (VI) dosages. It was observed that a concentration of 1 mM Fe (VI) maintained the pH stable at pH 9 while the removal rate was equivalent.

The combination and dosage chosen for the ISCO field testing was two injections of a solution 10 mM PS activated with 1 mM Fe (VI).

5.2.3 Laboratory testing for PFAS-polluted aquifer using ultrasonic cavitation

5.2.3.1 PFOS batch experiments

Based on the PFOS disappearance outcomes, attempts have been made to characterize the degradation by-products by performing the full-scan mass spectrometry analysis (Figure 19). Even if low-resolution mass spectrometry analysis doesn't allow the identification of by-products, some fragments have been identified as: (a) 62 m/z, (b) 147 m/z, (c) 157 m/z, (d) 210 m/z and (e) 244 m/z, which belong to the by-products. The fragments were identified in the dead volume of the chromatogram, which indicated that there was no retention on the chromatographic column and the fragments eluted simultaneously. Only linear structures that could arise during the PFOS bond scission have been proposed while other related PFAS short-chain structures have been disregarded. These compounds are therefore polar and lost the amphiphilic nature of PFOS followed by rapid scission via sonochemical treatment. The appearance of degraded products subsequently disappeared with a longer duration of treatment until 180 min. The intermediate products are believed to undergo a similar degradation mechanism as PFOS until the complete mineralization.

Figure 19 : Mass spectra of intermediate products formed after 60 min sonication

The extent of removal determined by UPLC-MS/MS analysis and mineralization (fluoride ion release) measured by IC analysis were very close to each other, indicating complete removal of PFOS using sonochemical treatment. Under optimum conditions, the degradation percentage determined by UPLC-MS/MS was 100 % and that for the IC was 99 %. The comparative outcome is depicted in Figure 20. The concentration of fluoride (F^-) started to increase with sonication and reached maximum by the end of treatment. Figure 21 shows the decline in PFOS concentration over the treatment time obtained from mass spectrometry and the fluoride evolution obtained from IC analysis. The maximum percentage of PFOS removal at 400 W/L was found to be 100% for the initial concentration of 5 mg/L, while the corresponding percentage of defluorination was 99%.

Figure 20 : Comparative outcome of PFOS removal vs mineralization

Figure 21 : Comparative outcome of PFOS (a) concentration decline vs (b) fluoride evolution

Considering the mineralization outcome and the appearance of degraded products starting from higher to lower molecular weight, the successive dissociation of CF_2 and the loss of sulfonate functional group from PFOS followed by the formation of fluorinated intermediates until complete defluorination is assumed to take place during sonication. During the mineralization, PFOS is expected to produce C1 fluoro-radicals, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide and fluoride ions as final products. PFOS is known as an anionic surfactant due to its hydrophilic (acid) tail and hydrophobic (perfluoroalkyl) head. The sonochemical degradation of a pollutant could take place in three different phases. The pollutant could travel to the bubble core and get pyrolyzed. It could also be present in bubble-liquid interfacial regions to follow thermal decomposition or remain in the liquid bulk phase for radical-driven degradation. The degradation mechanism is dependent on the nature of the

molecule. As PFOS is non-volatile, the chance of being transported into the bubble core and undergoing pyrolysis is limited. Therefore, the first dominant degradation pathway could be attributed to the interfacial thermal decomposition of PFOS followed by pyrolysis of short-chain degraded products inside the bubble-core, resulting in complete mineralization (Panda et al., 2019). Considering the faster mineralization rate of PFOS, the role of free radicals should be considered as negligible. For pollutants such as PFOS, which has very stable chemical bonds, high-temperature pyrolysis plays a vital role in its mineralization. The oxidizing radicals could not break down the stable C-F bond and initiate defluorination. Apart from that, the oxidative degradation pathway could result in a large number of intermediate formations, which could be adsorbed at the gas-liquid interface and hinder the pyrolytic degradation from taking place at the bubble core (Vecitis et al., 2008).

The complete PFOS removal was achieved under 500 kHz frequency with optimum parameters including initial pollutant concentration (5 mg/L), ultrasound power density (400 W/L) and solution temperature (25 °C) within 180 min of treatment. Under optimum conditions, 100% removal and 99% mineralization were achieved. The rate constant (k) ranged from 0.011 to 0.031 min^{-1} (first-order reaction), which increased with the increase in the power density. While the solution temperature did not significantly affect the PFOS removal efficiency, the initial concentration was found to have a prominent effect on the reaction rate constant. However, experiments at low frequency (22 kHz) showed negligible removal efficiency. The specific energy requirement for reaching 90% removal while considering the power consumed by the ultrasonic system from the main electrical source was determined to be 700 kWh/m^3 , which is much lower than other reported work under similar conditions. This work proved to be highly useful for our upscaling planning and groundwater treatment strategy.

5.2.3.2 AFFF and PFAS-contaminated groundwater batch experiments

Groundwater is a complex matrix containing various dissolved inorganic and organic constituents that can influence cavitation dynamics and degradation pathways. Therefore, understanding these interactions is essential for optimizing sonochemical treatment and improving its practical application in real-world scenarios. As the next steps of this project, high frequency (500 kHz) cavitation-based treatment of Aqueous film forming foam (AFFF) and PFAS-contaminated groundwater samples collected from Spain, have been conducted to understand the upscaling potential. The groundwater samples were collected from three monitoring wells (MW01, MW02, and MW05) located in Site 2 and sent to the laboratory for further studies. This study extended our understandings of PFOS removal and utilized the optimum reaction parameters (ex: solution temperature, treatment duration, power density) for the treatment of groundwater samples and AFFF mixture. The PFAS removal for AFFF mixture and groundwater samples was determined by using ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS) analyses. The perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) equivalent toxicity [SUM PFAS (ng PFOA-TEQ/L) and SUM PFAS (ng PFOA-CEQ/L)] of PFAS present in the groundwater before and after treatment were also determined.

The PFAS analysis detected 22 compounds, including PFOS, PFOA and PFBA, with concentrations ranging from 206 ng/L to 5574 ng/L (Table 14).

Table 14 : Detected PFAS compounds in the groundwater

Compound	PFAS concentration (ng/L)			LOQ (ng/L)
	MW1	MW2	MW05	
PFBA	306	356	532	10
PFPeA	717	731	1459	10
PFHxA	865	960	1385	10
PFHpA	142	183	321	10
PFOA	206	440	328	10
PFNA	<	<	21	10
PFDA	<	<	11	10
PFPrS	61	90	102	4
PFBS	245	374	365	10
PFPeS	201	352	348	10
PFHxS	1219	2196	2025	10
PFHpS	14	31	35	10
PFOS	541	4828	5574	10
PFNS	<	11	<	10
6:2 FTSA	2123	2608	3449	30
8:2 FTSA	35	84	88	20
10:2 FTSA	26	52	<	20
FBSA	154	369	358	10
FHxSA	74	135	209	10
PFHxSAM	<	50	<	20
6:2 FTAB	103	1560	1630	40
6:2 FTSaAM	<	134	<	60

Based on the UPLC-MS/MS results, a complete elimination of PFAS was found to be possible within 240 min of sonochemical treatment. As the experiments were conducted under identical operating conditions (P: 333 W/L, Solution temp.: 25 °C, treatment duration: 240 min), it has become feasible to compare the removal extent of individual PFAS compounds present in the groundwater to the stand-alone experiments including simulated PFOS and diluted AFFF formulation. Considering only groundwater samples, MW01 witnessed a 98% cumulative PFAS removal within 240 min of treatment time. At the same time, MW02 and MW05 have shown 96% and 99% removal. The sum PFAS removal rate constant (k) for MW01, MW02 and MW05 were 0.0164, 0.0135 and 0.0199 min⁻¹ (first-order reaction), respectively. Figure 22 presents the progress in groundwater PFAS removal over the treatment duration.

Figure 22 : (a) MW01, (b) MW02 and (c) MW05: PFAS removal over 240 min treatment time.

As the groundwater samples were found to contain significant amount of PFOS (8% of MW1 and 31% of MW2 and MW5 total PFAS concentration), it is ideal to compare its removal efficiency to the simulated PFOS removal efficiency under identical operating conditions, which could demonstrate the influence of inorganics and co-contaminants. Therefore, we have compared the PFOS removal efficiency present in the groundwater (MW1: 0.5 µg/L, MW2: 4.8 µg/L, MW5: 5.6 µg/L) to the earlier conducted experiments on simulated PFOS solution under identical conditions (PFOS initial concentration: 2 and 100 µg/L). At an energy input of 333 W/L, the simulated PFOS removal efficiency reached 93% (k : 0.0121 min⁻¹) for 2 µg/L and 93% (k : 0.0114 min⁻¹) for 100 µg/L. Under the same conditions, for the MW01 with initial PFOS concentration of 0.5 µg/L, the maximum PFOS removal efficiency reached 93% (k : 0.0112 min⁻¹). At the same time, for MW02 and MW05, the PFOS removal efficiency was found to be 92% (k : 0.0102 min⁻¹) and 98% (k : 0.0151 min⁻¹), respectively. The increase in PFOS removal efficiency could be attributed to the increase in the initial concentration. The decline in PFAS removal under low initial concentration could be attributed to the limited availability of PFAS molecules at the bubble interface, hindering the mineralization process. As demonstrated by our earlier research, this trend was found to be identical and hence, conclusions can be drawn on this aspect. As the difference in PFOS removal is not found to be statistically significant across all the groundwater samples and the simulated PFOS, the influence of inorganics present in the groundwater could be assumed to be negligible.

Similarly, as the AFFF formulation consists of identical PFAS compounds present in the groundwater samples (PFBA, PFHxA, 6:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, 10:2 FTSA, 6:2 FTAB, 6:2 FTSaAM), we have undertaken AFFF sonochemical treatments to understand the influence of inorganics present (Cations: Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Na⁺ and anions: Br⁻, Cl⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻) in the groundwater. The initial AFFF concentration of 2 µg/L was chosen for the experiment to have an ideal comparison with the groundwater samples. All other operating parameters (solution temperature, ultrasound frequency, and power density) were kept constant. The simulated AFFF removal efficiency was found to be 92%, whereas the cumulative removal efficiency of identical compounds (sum of compounds) in MW01 and MW02 reached 99% and 100% for MW5. This could be attributed to the higher initial concentration in groundwater (MW1: 3.5 µg/L, MW2: 5.7 µg/L, MW5: 7 µg/L) compared to the diluted AFFF solution (2 µg/L). This trend is also identical to our hypothesis that the increase in initial concentration drives the removal rate of PFAS. Therefore, the role of inorganics should be disregarded when looking at the comparative results of PFOS and AFFF.

Following the PFAS CALUX bioanalysis report from BDS, the PFOA toxicological equivalents were calculated. Considering MW1, based on the calculated data, the PFOA toxicological equivalents are as follows: BEQ [4800 ng PFOA-BEQ/L] > CEQ [3600 ng PFOA-CEQ/L] > TEQ [2200 ng PFOA-TEQ/L]. However, for MW2, it was found to be in the order of CEQ [14320 ng PFOA-CEQ/L] > BEQ [13000 ng PFOA-BEQ/L] > TEQ [11440 ng PFOA-TEQ/L] and for MW5, it was in the order of CEQ [16000 ng PFOA-CEQ/L] > TEQ [13000 ng PFOA-TEQ/L] > BEQ [6000 ng PFOA-BEQ/L]. Comparing the PFOA-TEQ and PFOA-CEQ with PFOA-BEQ, it can be inferred that for MW5, the TEQ as well as CEQ are higher than BEQ and for MW3, the TEQ, BEQ and CEQ values are not significantly different. Therefore, PFOS remains as the main driver of toxicity for those samples as it contributes 84% and 85% to the total

PFAS impact. However, for MW1, as the BEQ is higher than TEQ (2 times higher) and also higher than CEQ, more PFAS congeners would need to be identified as the driver of toxicity to fill-up the gap between PFAS CALUX analysis results and chemical analysis converted TEQ and CEQ. Therefore, we disregarded the PFOA toxicity equivalents determination of MW1 samples subjected to sonochemical treatment. However, for MW2 and MW5, as $TEQ \text{ and } CEQ \geq BEQ$, PFOA toxicity equivalents in terms of TEQ or CEQ are calculated to estimate the overall toxicity of the samples over the treatment time. Considering MW2, the total PFAS toxicity (SUM PFAS of 14 compounds) was found to decline from 11440 [ng PFOA-TEQ/L] to 990 [ng PFOA-TEQ/L] and 14320 [ng PFOA-CEQ/L] to 930 [ng PFOA-CEQ/L] within 240 min of treatment. Similarly, for MW5, the total PFAS toxicity was found to decline from 13000 [ng PFOA-TEQ/L] to 450 [ng PFOA-TEQ/L] and 16000 [ng PFOA-CEQ/L] to 320 [ng PFOA-CEQ/L] within 240 min of treatment.

Under optimum conditions (solution temperature, power density), the total PFAS concentration of MW-1, MW-2 and MW-5 groundwater samples declined by 98%, 96%, and 99%, respectively, within 240 min of treatment, which indicated first-order reaction kinetics. The study also compares the groundwater outcomes with the Aqueous film forming foam (AFFF) and simulated perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) solution under identical treatment conditions. Unlike earlier reports, the presence of inorganic matters did not affect the PFAS elimination. PFOA equivalent toxicity [SUM PFAS (ng PFOA-TEQ/L) and SUM PFAS (ng PFOA-CEQ/L)] of the groundwater PFAS before and after treatment indicated the toxicity to decline significantly. The next step would be to conduct experiments with an up-scaled continuous cavitation device and compare its outcome.

5.3 ISCO Field testing

5.3.1 Tracer test

From the tracer test conducted, salinity profiles (point dilution tests) were carried out in order to obtain the actual velocity of the groundwater flow. Salinity profiles in the injection well were performed just after injection, and after injection at 3 h on May 2, at 24 h on May 3, at 92 h on May 6 and at 240 h on May 13, 2024.

In the following graph, the evolution of the salinity profiles over time at the injection point can be seen:

Time evolution of electrical conductivity in MW01

Figure 23 : Conductivity evolution in control point MW1

From the previous profile, two distinct segments can be observed, indicating preferential flow pathways. A velocity of 0.08 m/day was calculated for the shallower segment (up to 6.5 meters depth), while a velocity of 0.006 m/day was determined for the deeper segment. Across the entire saturated zone, an average velocity of 0.019 m/day was obtained at point MW1.

Salinity profiles in the observation wells were performed before injection, and after injection at 3 h on May 2, at 24 h on May 3, at 92 h on May 6 and at 240 h on May 13. The following graphs illustrate the evolution of the salinity profiles at the observation points of the test:

Time evolution of electrical conductivity in MW2

Figure 24 : Conductivity evolution in control point MW2

Time evolution of electrical conductivity in MW05

Figure 25 : Conductivity evolution in control point MW5

As can be seen in the previous graphs, in the observation wells MW2 and MW5, a differentiated behaviour of the injected water mass is also observed, influenced by the various lithologies present at the site.

A preferential flow of the solute through the upper layers of the subsurface is detected, with higher permeabilities and velocities in the segments up to 7-8 meters depth, composed of pebbles in a 30% silty clay gravel matrix. In MW2, it is clearly observed that 3 hours after the test was conducted, the solute preferentially migrated through this more superficial layer. In contrast, the deeper layer exhibits lower hydraulic flow velocities. This layer is composed of silty clay sand with gravel.

Furthermore, the interpretation of the tracer test at the observation points has allowed for the estimation of transport parameters, which are presented in the following table:

Table 15 : Main data obtained from the tracer test

Piezometer	Advective Velocity (m/d)	Porosity (%)	Dispersivity (m)
MW02	2.30	0.36	7.38 ± 4.38
MW05	0.27	3.2	9.09±3.88
MW01	0.019		-

It is important to note that in the observation well MW04, the influence of the tracer was not detected.

The interpretation of the tests has allowed for the estimation of an injected flow velocity ranging from 2.3 to 0.012 m/day, a dispersivity of 7 to 9 m²/day, and medium porosities between 0.36% and 3.2%. These values are representative of the heterogeneity present at the site, which exhibits very low permeabilities (ranging from K=1.3 m/d to K=3.1·10⁻⁴ m/d).

5.3.2 In situ remediation

In total, two campaigns of oxidant injections were conducted, consisting of two series of 3 injections each (6 injections in total), carried out at 0h, 8h, and 24h in well MW1. PFAS concentrations were monitored in wells MW2 and MW5, at 0h, 4h, 8h, 32h, 2 weeks, and 3 weeks for well MW2, and at 0h, 4 days, 2 weeks, and 3 weeks for well MW5. Sampling times were estimated by the flow velocity determined in 5.3.1.

The first campaign of chemical oxidant injection into the saturated zone of the subsurface was carried out on July 8 and 9, 2024, and the second campaign of oxidant injection was conducted on July 29 and 30, 2024 (20 days apart).

In the first set of injections, a total volume of 200L was prepared for each injection in a drum containing tap water with a 10mM PS + 1mM Fe(VI) reagent mixture. In the second set of injections, the same injection volume was used, but the dose of PS and ferrate was tripled, 30mM PS + 3mM Fe(VI).

Measurement of in-situ groundwater parameters (temperature, pH, conductance and Redox potential) was done previously to the groundwater sampling. All parameters were within normal and expected ranges. The following table shows the values obtained for the physicochemical parameters (pH, temperature, electrical conductivity and Redox potential) at the monitoring points on site.

Table 16 : Groundwater In-situ physicochemical parameters

Sampling well	Date	pH (U. pH)	Temperature (°C)	Conductance (µS/cm)	Dissolved oxygen (mg/l)	ORP (mV)
MW-2	08/07/2024	7.07	19.3	703	3.35	58.6
	09/07/2024 (4h)	7.53	24.1	948	3.17	161.7
	09/07/2024 (8h)	7.10	20.9	873	2.57	198.8
	10/07/2024	7.80	24.3	903	3.24	213.8
	12/07/2024	7.28	19.4	720	2.8	89.3
	17/07/2024	6.82	19.9	683	3.8	138,0
	23/07/2024	7.14	19.4	650	2.8	111.8
	29/07/2024	6.57	20.1	593	2.35	36.8
	30/07/2024	7.14	20.2	834	2.1	22.8
	01/08/2024	6.81	21.1	671	2.1	152.1
	07/08/2024	7.29	19.8	1981	3.1	254.2
	14/08/2024	6.72	19.2	1334	1.96	267.6
	MW-5	08/07/2024	7.56	18.6	681	1.51
12/07/2024		6.82	19.3	692	3.3	101.3
17/07/2024		7.02	19.7	684	2.1	141.0
23/07/2024		6.72	18.5	684	2.4	110.9
29/07/2024		7.17	19.0	659	1.9	57.9
01/08/2024		7.12	21.8	728	2.9	171.2

Sampling well	Date	pH (U. pH)	Temperature (°C)	Conductance (µS/cm)	Dissolved oxygen (mg/l)	ORP (mV)
	07/08/2024	7.83	20.5	1540	3.2	201.3
	14/08/2024	6.59	18.9	1016	2.4	312.0
MW-1	08/07/2024	7.99	19.4	828	2.73	-4.7
	17/07/2024	6.71	19.3	1784	3.9	242.3
	23/07/2024	6.54	19.5	1789	1.5	241.8
	29/07/2024	6.32	20.1	1070	2.6	75.5
	07/08/2024	7.17	20.6	2330	2.4	342.6
	14/08/2024	6.23	19.4	1370	2.24	408.4

Below, the evolution of the removal efficiencies of the main groups of PFAS, associated with the chemical oxidation treatment, is shown.

Figure 26 : Evolution of PFAS concentrations at the injection point MW1 during the in-situ oxidation treatment

Figure 27 : Evolution of individual PFAS concentrations at the injection point MW1 during the in-situ oxidation treatment

PFAS of carbon chain lengths ≤ 6 detected in MW1 just prior to the field testing were, from the most abundant PFAS compound to the less: PFHxS, PFHxA, PFPeA, PFBS, PFPeS, PFBA, and 4:2-FTS, and the main PFAS with $C > 6$ were: PFOS, 6:2-FTS, PFOA, PFHpA, PFHpS, PFNS, PFDA, and PFNA. At the injection well MW1, a decrease in PFAS concentrations was observed following both sets of injections. It is important to note that the oxidizing agent is only effective in the environment for 2 weeks, which would explain the increase in concentrations detected 3-weeks after both first and second set of injections. As it can be seen in Figure 27, this sharp increase 3 weeks after the second injection is mainly due to the occurrence of 6:2-FTS. One hypothesis to explain this fact, might be the desorption of specific PFAS, and specially 6:2-FTS, from the soil matrix in the unsaturated area of the aquifer. Since 6:2-FTS is a precursor, it cannot be a degradation by-product caused by the treatment. Fire-fighting trainings using AFFF during the period of this field testing are discarded.

For the calculation of treatment efficiencies at MW1, the initial concentrations and the concentrations detected 2 weeks after the injection were considered. The first set of injections showed a treatment efficiency of 61% for total PFAS, 67% for long-chain PFAS, and 52% for short-chain PFAS. The efficiencies detected in the second set of injections were 94% for the total detected PFAS, 96% for long-chain PFAS, and 92% for short-chain PFAS. These removal efficiencies might be masked by the potential desorption of contaminants from the soil matrix during the oxidant treatment.

It is worth noting that the increase in pH observed in the lab was not reproduced at field scale. Prior to the injection, pH in MW1 was 7.99, and after the injection this decreased being 6.23 the lowest value observed at the end of the field testing.

Figure 28 : Evolution of PFAS concentrations at the monitoring well MW2 during the in-situ oxidation treatment

Figure 29 : Evolution of individual PFAS concentrations at the monitoring well MW2 during the in-situ oxidation treatment

Regarding the observation point MW2, located 12 meters away, it is observed that the first pulse of both injections caused an increase in PFAS in groundwater during the first hours (4 and 8 hours) likely due to the oxidizing agents' high capacity to enhance the desorption processes of contaminants adsorbed in the soil matrix (i.e., in this case mainly due to PFOS desorption). Subsequently, after 32h

of the first injection, a sharp decrease in PFAS was observed, considering the initial increase. In this first set of injections, a significant decrease in concentrations was observed, with efficiencies of 97.6% for long-chain PFAS, 76.5% for short-chain PFAS, and 96.7% for total PFAS compounds detected.

During the second injection, after 4 hours, the most abundant PFAS compound in MW2 was 6:2-FTS. According to the obtained data, the oxidizing agents remain effective up to 32 hours, during which concentrations decrease with efficiencies of 77.7% for long-chain PFAS, 29.0% for short-chain PFAS, and an overall efficiency of 76.9%. After 32 hours, the PFAS concentrations raised again mainly due to the presence of 6:2-FTS.

In MW2, pH ranged between 6.57 and 7.80 throughout the field testing.

Figure 30 : Evolution of PFAS concentrations at the monitoring well MW5 during the in-situ oxidation treatment

Figure 31 : Evolution of PFAS concentrations at the monitoring well MW5 during the in-situ oxidation treatment

At the most distant observation point, MW5 (located 20 meters away), the first injection has almost no effect on the PFAS concentrations in the well. Treatment efficiencies of 29.6% for long-chain PFAS, 11.8% for short-chain PFAS, and 19.6% for the total PFAS were detected. However, all PFAS compounds decreased except for PFPeA, which is the most abundant PFAS after 3 weeks of the first injection, which can be formed due to the breakdown of longer PFAS. However, in the second injection, where the dose of the oxidizing agents was tripled, an increase in contaminant concentrations was observed due to soil desorption processes (i.e., mainly 6:2-FTS). Subsequently, after two weeks, treatment efficiencies of 91% for long-chain PFAS, 58% for short-chain PFAS, and 83% for the total PFAS were achieved. It is important to note that after the second week, the oxidizing agent is depleted in the environment, and no further effects are observed.

5.3.3 Toxicological assays

During the field testing, samples for toxicological assays were taken from MW1, MW2 and MW5. In Table 15, the final PFAS CALUX analysis results for the samples extracted using WAX-SPE are summarised. For all samples, the CALUX results are expressed as the concentration of PFOA equivalents per litre of processed water. Graphical representation of all PFAS CALUX bioanalysis results is presented in Annex IV.

For all samples, the activity was above the activity found in the procedure blank. Furthermore, the PFAS activity in all samples exceeded the Evidence-based toxicology (EBT) derived for drinking water (DW) and surface water (SW). As expected, the exceedance of the drinking water and surface water EBTs was lowest for the blank sample (0.13 and 0.09 times, respectively).

Table 17 : CALUX analysis results of groundwater in MW1, MW2 and MW5 during the in-situ remediation

BDS code	client code	PFAS CALUX		Activity > PB	Fold EBT exceedance	
		activity	LOQ		EBT - DW	EBT - SW
(-)	(-)	BEQ (ug PFOA/l sample)		(-)	(-)	(-)
49797	MW1 - pre-injection	17	0.17	yes	5.6	3.9
49798	MW1 - after 1st injection	6.5	0.081	yes	2.1	1.5
49799	MW1 - after 2nd injection	5.1	0.10	yes	1.7	1.2
49800	MW2 - pre-injection	9.3	0.16	yes	3.1	2.1
49801	MW2 - after 1st injection	1.0	0.088	yes	0.29	0.20
49802	MW2 - after 2nd injection	6.0	0.088	yes	2.0	1.4
49803	MW5 - pre-injection	9.8	0.073	yes	3.2	2.3
49804	MW5 - after 1st injection	4.9	0.082	yes	1.6	1.1
49805	MW5 - after 2nd injection	8.0	0.089	yes	2.6	1.8
49806	Blank	0.51	0.083	yes	0.13	0.09
PB		0.12	0.094			
EBT - DW		3.0				
EBT - SW		4.3				

Note: evaluation of CALUX bioassay analysis results after correction for activity in procedure blank (HPLC-water)

Table 18 shows toxicity reductions compared to the total PFAS concentrations at each monitoring well after the first and second set of oxidant injections are shown.

Table 18 : Toxicity and concentration reduction during ISCO field testing

	CALUX Activity µg PFOA/l sample	Toxicity Reduction	µg/l 16 PFAS	Concentration reduction
Blank	0.51			
MW1 pre injection	17		244	
MW1 after 1st injection 3w	6.5	61.76%	162	33.4%
MW1 after 2nd injection 3w	5.1	70.00%	748	-207%
MW2 pre injection	9.3		49	
MW2 after 1st injection 3w	1.0	89.25%	18	62.5%
MW2 after 2nd injection 3w	6.0	35.48%	687	-1295%
MW5 pre injection	9.8		100	
MW5 after 1st injection 3w	4.9	50.00%	68	31.9%
MW5 after 2nd injection 3 w	8.0	18.37%	648	-548%

The overall toxicity reduction was about 62 and 70% in MW1, 35 and 89% in MW2 and 18 and 50% in MW5. Removal PFAS concentrations do not correlate with toxicity reduction, suggesting that PFAS potentially desorbed from the soil matrix, such as 6:2-FTS, are less toxic than its degradation products.

The observed toxicity of water after ISCO was still above drinking and surface waters quality. However, PFAS concentrations measured in the wells after the treatment were also well above current quality standards for drinking water (11.5, 13.4 and 18.4 µg/L in MW5, MW1 and MW2, respectively).

5.3.4 Conclusions of the field testing

The characterization of the hydraulic parameters of the site through tracer tests led to the conclusion that the medium was heterogeneous and anisotropic, with very low permeability and limited dispersion of potential contaminants or solutes, which complicates the injection of oxidants.

Regarding the in-situ remediation efforts, based on the data presented earlier, obtained during the pilot tests of chemical oxidation in groundwater, the following aspects are highlighted:

- It is worth noting that, in general, the injections initially caused an increase in PFAS concentrations in the groundwater potentially due to the high capacity of oxidants to enhance the desorption processes of contaminants adsorbed in the soil matrix. Furthermore, once the oxidizing agent is depleted through oxidation processes with the high mass of contaminants, organic matter, and/or other natural compounds present in the medium, the contaminants in the subsurface matrix re-equilibrate with groundwater.
- Subsequently, a decrease in PFAS concentrations was observed in the treatment zone, primarily for long-chain PFAS and, to a lesser extent, for short-chain PFAS, as the degradation of long-chain PFAS can produce short-chain PFAS.

- Based on the analytical results obtained during the pilot test, the removal efficiency of PFAS 2 weeks after the injections in the saturated zone of the upper subsurface was determined to be between 32-63%.
- Reductions on toxicity were also observed after both oxidant injections, ranging from 18 to 89%.
- Since the target analytical method for PFAS used in the present study included up to 41 compounds, the full mineralization of PFAS compounds due to the oxidation action cannot be assured. However, the reductions observed in the toxicological assays, suggests that at least no degradation by-products (i.e., ultra short PFAS) are being formed with toxic effects superior to those of the parent compounds.

6 Conclusions

VOC-polluted site (Site 1). The treatment strategy was based on the effectiveness of **eight novel oxidation treatments**, including persulfate (PS), ferrous sulfate, sulfidated nano-zero valent iron (S-nZVI), and potassium ferrate, along with their combinations. The results obtained at lab-scale indicated that the PS and S-nZVI combination with 10 mM oxidizing agent and 5-hour of reaction time effectively removed contaminants in synthetic groundwater (89% DCE, 87% TCE, 59% PCE). In **real groundwater**, performance decreased, with 94% TCE and 73% PCE removal over 5 hours. A 24-hour spiked experiment achieved **69% DCE, 99% TCE, and 92% PCE removal** without harmful by-products. The findings suggest longer reaction times may be needed for complete chlorinated solvent removal in real groundwater, and further field-scale studies are necessary for real-world applications.

For the **PFAS-polluted site** (Site 2), two different treatment strategies were tested for PFAS remediation, one **in-situ using oxidation reagents** and the other **on-site** using the oxidation potential of the **ultrasonic cavitation**.

Worth mentioning that the PFAS-polluted site is still active with ongoing fire-fighting trainings using AFFF. Measured PFAS concentrations in groundwater at the beginning of the project were up to 130 µg/L, but during the field testing, concentrations up to more than 700 µg/L were observed. However, during the period of the field testing (July and August 2024), fire-fighting trainings were not conducted.

In order to adjust the in-situ chemical oxidation, a first period of lab testing was performed in order to select the best oxidant combination and dosages to degrade PFAS. The designed workflow consisted of first tests with synthetic groundwater that mimicked the groundwater from Site 2, then with real groundwater and finally with real groundwater and soil from the site, in batch and column. Lab-scale experiments demonstrated that the best option for PFAS removal from groundwater using an ISCO strategy was **the use of PS activated with Fe(VI)**, in front of the activation of persulfate with nZVI. However, at lab scale, the maximum removal obtained was ca. 37% and the full mineralization of PFAS was not assured. The combination and dosage chosen for the ISCO field testing were two sets of injections separated in 20 days of a solution 10 mM PS activated with 1 mM Fe (VI) and 30 mM PS with 3 mM Fe (VI), for the first and second sets of injections, respectively.

In the ISCO field testing, the subsurface conditions at the site were not optimal for oxidation processes via point injections, since the characterization of the hydraulic parameters of the site indicated very low permeability and limited dispersion of potential contaminants or solutes. Medium efficiencies of PFAS removal were observed 2 weeks after the injections, at the injection well MW1, **82% for long-chain PFAS (C>6) and 72% for short-chain PFAS (C≤6)**. In contrast, low efficiencies were observed in the monitoring wells MW2 and MW5, since the potential desorption of PFAS from the soil matrix might be high in these two wells, with a high increase of 6:2-FTS and PFOS in groundwater after the injections. However, the overall **toxicity reduction observed in all three wells ranged from 18 to 89%**, suggesting that even the full mineralization of PFAS cannot be assured, at least no degradation by-products (i.e., ultra short PFAS) were being formed during the oxidation process with

toxic effects superior to those of the parent compounds. For further tests, the assessment of the full mineralization should be considered by the monitoring of fluorides during the testing.

The pilot test also demonstrated that the injected oxidant potentially promoted the desorption of contaminants retained in the subsurface. The main desorbed PFAS were PFOS and 6:2-FTS. The assessment of the ISCO efficiency at field scale was difficult due to these desorption effects, which masked the real PFAS degradation.

Final concentrations of PFAS and EBT achieved at the end of the ISCO testing were above quality standards for DW or SW (100 ng 20 PFAS/L and 0.65 ng PFOS/L, respectively). For the specific conditions of Site 2, this in-situ remediation approach would not be fully effective or appropriate. PFAS treatment via ISCO might be appropriate for a site with higher water permeability and lower initial PFAS levels.

In conclusion, further studies are necessary to assess the effectiveness of ISCO using PS with Fe (VI) for an in situ PFAS-contaminated groundwater remediation strategy. Main uncertainties still present are the following:

- Need to distinguish between PFAS removal due to sorption to ferric compounds from PFAS degradation.
- Longer experiments at field-scale are needed in order to test if there are clogging issues in the aquifer due to the generation of ferric compounds.
- To test if the oxidizing agents PS and Fe(VI) can desorb PFAS from the soil matrix and change the geochemical conditions of the aquifer (pH, redox, etc.).

The on-site treatment strategy based on ultrasonic cavitation have shown excellent results. High-frequency (500 kHz) operation resulted in the complete removal of PFOS within just 180 min of treatment. Under identical operating conditions, PFAS present in groundwater samples, witnessed up to **99% removal within 240 min of treatment**. Given the consistent effectiveness of cavitation-based treatment in treating PFAS, our goal is to evaluate the upscaling of ultrasound treatment, which could continuously treat PFAS contaminated water in a cost-effective way. Thus, careful optimization of bench-scale experiments will be undertaken while considering factors such as ultrasound reactor geometry, transducer types and the physicochemical properties of the matrix. The design challenge, which remains the greatest difficulty in upscaling ultrasound-based treatments, will be addressed by implementing advanced computer interface to optimize ultrasound parameters. Future research and development with proper optimization could pave the way for ultrasound to be implemented in real-world scenarios.

7 Literature

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Annexes

Annex I. Groundwater characterization (Site 1)

Sample name	Depth	Temperature	pH	Conductivity	O ₂	Eh
	m	°C		mS/cm	mg/L	mV
Well "Pozo"	6.21	16.8	7.40	0.42	2.38	65.9
MW-2	7.19	16.3	7.49	1.44	0.82	-68.5
MW-6	7.325	17.3	5.21	57.60	1.33	69.2
MW-14	7.415	19.1	5.52	11.68	5.32	158.7

Sample name	TSS	TOC	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	Br ⁻	Cl ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻
	mg/L											
Well "Pozo"	15	<2	44	2	19	11	<0.1	72	<0.1	0.6	5.1	71
MW-2	979	3	104	20	14	139	<0.2	212	<0.2	0.8	109	209
MW-6	2336	<50	5820	521	41	244	<20	24600	<20	216	81	-
MW-14	103	<10	1990	175	12	186	<2.0	5410	<2.0	259	128	-
MW Field Blank Site 1	<1.5	<50	<0.5	<0.25	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.25	<0.1	<0.5	<0.4	-
Transport Blank Site 1	<1.5	<1	<0.5	<0.25	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.25	<0.1	<0.5	<0.4	-

Sample name	Cd	Co	Pb	Zn	Fe	Ni	V	Cu	Ba	Mn	As
	µg/L										
Well "Pozo"	<1	2	<5	1970	<50	<5	<0.5	<5	432	3510	<1
MW-2	<1	5	<5	110	360	8	<0.5	<5	550	4420	7
MW-6	302	990	83	3091000	1842000	6930	<5	3050	1830	116000	<10
MW-14	42	226	24	267000	3950	782	<5	170	498	34400	<10
MW Field Blank	<0.5	<0.5	<2.5	<25	<25	<2.5	<0.25	<2.5	<1	<1	<0.5
MW Transport Blank	<0.5	<0.5	<2.5	<25	<25	<2.5	<0.25	<2.5	<1	<1	<0.5

Annex II: Groundwater characterization (Site 2)

Sample name	GW Depth	Temperature	pH	Conductivity	O ₂	Eh
	m	°C		uS/cm	mg/L	mV
MW01	5.91	17.5	6.86	692	1.74	136.7
MW02	6.15	16.3	6.87	643	1.93	142.4
MW03	6.605	17.4	6.82	915	1.86	120
MW04	5.87	17.2	6.89	906	1.86	146
MW05	6.353	18.1	6.89	616	1.64	92.6
MW06	5.945	16.2	7.56	355	1.17	112.5

Sample name	TSS	TOC	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	Br ⁻	Cl ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻
	mg/L											
MW01	860	3	81	16	3	34	0.2	45	<0.1	22	42	164
MW02	546	2	66	13	3	30	0.2	44	<0.1	21	37	133
MW03	2908	2	107	25	3	40	0.3	49	<0.2	15	50	226
MW04	988	6	110	28	2.9	33	<0.2	34	<0.2	0.7	21	238
MW05	2906	2	71	12	3	31	0.2	44	<0.1	18	33	138
MW06	3720	<2	33	7	3	21	<0.1	25	<0.1	5.1	23	68
MW Field Blank	<1.5	<2	<0.5	<0.25	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.25	<0.1	<0.5	<0.4	NA
MW Transport Blank	<1.5	<1	<0.5	<0.25	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.25	<0.1	<0.5	<0.4	NA

Sample name	Cd	Co	Pb	Zn	Fe	Ni	V	Cu	Ba	Mn	As
	µg/L										
MW01	<1	<1	<5	101	<50	<5	<0.5	<5	144	102	<1
MW02	<1	<1	<5	<50	<50	<5	<0.5	<5	117	8	<1
MW03	<1	2	<5	<50	<50	3	<0.5	<5	169	179	<1
MW04	<1	6	<5	<50	<50	11	<0.5	<5	198	1470	2
MW05	<1	3	<5	<50	95	<5	<0.5	<5	109	254	<1
MW06	<1	<1	<5	<50	<50	<5	<0.5	<5	80	2	<1
MW Field Blank	<0.5	<0.5	<2.5	<25	<25	<2.5	<0.25	<2.5	<1	<1	<0.5
MW Transport Blank	<0.5	<0.5	<2.5	<25	<25	<2.5	<0.25	<2.5	<1	<1	<0.5

Annex III: Soil characterization (Site 2)

Sample name	Moisture	Al	Si	S	K	Ca	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn
	%													
MW4 2.7m	12.66	5.420	16.272	0.016	1.975	<LOD	0.535	0.008	0.019	0.058	3.758	0.004	0.003	0.014
MW4 5m	3.36	6.003	14.745	0.011	2.082	<LOD	0.405	0.005	0.021	0.068	3.507	0.005	0.002	0.014
MW4 9.15m	6.29	6.099	16.885	0.008	2.510	0.548	0.387	0.010	0.020	0.091	3.177	0.004	0.004	0.013
MW5 2.9m	18.56	5.204	18.000	0.020	1.890	<LOD	0.517	0.008	0.015	0.055	3.670	0.005	0.003	0.012
MW5 5.10m	3.87	5.919	17.522	0.009	2.268	<LOD	0.419	0.007	0.018	0.048	4.058	0.004	0.003	0.015
MW5 9m	9.11	5.881	15.186	0.009	2.494	0,061	0.486	0.015	0.018	0.079	4.009	0.005	0.005	0.021
Blank		1.008	1.706	<LOD	<LOD	0,127	<LOD	<LOD	0.036	0.022	0.126	0.003	<LOD	0.003

Annex IV: Graphical representation of PFAS CALUX analysis

Graphical representation of the PFAS CALUX analysis results of serial dilutions of groundwater sample extracts. Results are expressed as induction of luminescence, relative to the maximum response of the reference compound PFOA.

